

**Catalogue of Lepidoptera of Omsk Region (Russia).
Microlepidoptera. Families: Eriocraniidae,
Nepticulidae, Opostegidae, Adelidae, Prodoxidae,
Incurvariidae, Psychidae, Tineidae, Roeslerstammiidae,
Bucculatricidae, Gracillariidae, Yponomeutidae,
Argyresthiidae, Plutelliidae, Acrolepiidae,
Glyphipterigidae, Ypsolophidae, Lyonetiidae,
Bedelliidae, Ethmiidae, Depressariidae, Elachistidae,
Parametriotidae, Scythrididae, Chimabachidae,
Cryptolechiidae, Oecophoridae, Batrachedridae,
Coleophoridae, Momphidae, Blastobasidae,
Autostichidae, Cosmopterigidae, Gelechiidae,
Pterophoridae, Epermeniidae, Choreutidae,
Galacticidae, Tortricidae, Pyralidae, Crambidae**

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Abstract

A total of 781 species of Microlepidoptera belonging to 41 families are reported for the territory of Omsk Region. The most numerous is the Tortricidae family represented by 255 species, then Crambidae (94 species), Gelechiidae (70), Pyralidae (66), Pterophoridae (44), Depressariidae (32), Gracillariidae (29), Tineidae (25), Elachistidae (14), Adelidae and Elachistidae (8 species in each family), Yponomeutidae, Ypsolophidae, Ethmiidae and Cosmopterigidae (7 species in each family), Scythrididae and Oecophoridae (6 species in each family), Eriocraniidae (4), Nepticulidae, Momphidae and Epermeniidae (3 species in each family), Prodoxidae, Glyphipterigidae, Lyonetiidae and Choreutidae (2 species in each family), Opostegidae, Incurvariidae, Roeslerstammiidae, Argyrorethiidae, Plutelliidae, Acrolepiidae, Bedelliidae, Parametriotidae, Chimabachidae, Cryptolechiidae, Batrachedridae, Blastobasidae, Autostichidae, Galacticidae (1 species in each family). 10 species are new to the Omsk Region. *Agonopterix purpurea* (Haworth, 1811) and *Aethes flagellana* (Duponchel, 1836) are reported from the territory of Omsk Region as new to the Asian Part of Russia; *Fomoria weaveri* (Stainton, 1855) reported from the territory of West Siberia for the first time.

Keywords

Russia, West Siberia, Omsk Region, Lepidoptera, Catalogue, Eriocraniidae, Nepticulidae, Opostegidae, Adelidae, Prodoxidae, Incurvariidae, Psychidae, Tineidae, Roeslerstammiidae, Bucculatricidae, Gracillariidae, Yponomeutidae, Argyrorethiidae, Plutelliidae, Acrolepiidae, Glyphipterigidae, Ypsolophidae, Lyonetiidae, Bedelliidae, Ethmiidae, Depressariidae, Elachistidae, Parametriotidae, Scythrididae, Chimabachidae, Cryptolechiidae, Oecophoridae, Batrachedridae, Coleophoridae, Momphidae, Blastobasidae, Autostichidae, Cosmopterigidae, Gelechiidae, Pterophoridae, Epermeniidae, Choreutidae, Galacticidae, Tortricidae, Pyralidae, Crambidae

Introduction

The second Part of the Catalogue of Lepidoptera of Omsk Region of Russia is dedicated to the large complex of families of Microlepidoptera. The geographical location (Fig. 1) and landscape characteristics of the territory of Omsk Region were considered in the first part of the Catalogue (Knyazev 2020). Main landscapes of forest, forest-steppe and steppe zones are illustrated on the figures 3–8.

The first attempts to take an inventory of the region's Lepidoptera (including Microlepidoptera) fauna were undertaken by S.D. Lavrov in the beginning of XX century. In his article (Lavrov 1927) he mentions 2 species of Psychidae, 39 species of Pyralidae and Crambidae, 2 species of Pterophoridae, 23 species of Tortricidae and 15 species of other Microlepidoptera families. After that almost 90 years later there were some faunistic lists and small additions to them by different Microlepidoptera families published: Gracillariidae (Knyazev et al. 2018, 2019), Coleophoridae (Anikin and Knyazev 2012, 2016, 2021), Ethmiidae (Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012; Knyazev et al. 2015), Depressariidae (Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012, 2013, 2016; Knyazev et al. 2015, 2018, 2019), Cryptolechiidae (Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012), Chimabachidae (Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012), Oecophoridae (Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012; Knyazev et al. 2015, 2018, 2019), Autostichidae (Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012),

Gelechiidae (Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020), Tortricidae (Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019), Galactiidae (Knyazev et al. 2016), Pterophoridae (Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013; Knyazev et al. 2018, 2019), Thyrididae (Knyazev et al. 2016), Crambidae (Knyazev et al. 2014, 2016, 2018, 2019, 2021; Knyazev and Ponomaryov 2019) and Pyralidae (Knyazev et al. 2014, 2018, 2019). In the end of 2021 a large work on 27 families of Microlepidoptera was published (Sinev and Knyazev 2021).

Figure 1. Location of the Omsk Region in Northern Eurasia.

Material and methods

We analyzed all known faunistic publications on Lepidoptera of the Omsk Oblast from 1927 to 2021. The author's private collection as the largest regional collection of Lepidoptera in the Omsk Oblast served as the principal database for compiling the catalogue.

The daylight species were collected by means of butterfly net, moths with the night activity were attracting to the mercury lamps 250W, already with UV-traps.

The taxonomy is accepted according to the new edition of the Lepidoptera Catalog of Russia (Sinev 2019). We have included some information in the text for each species. This information was coded by: REF – bibliographic references reported the species in the region; LOC – localities where the species was registered; FP – imago flight period (conventionally, months of flight are indicated in Roman numerals). Species firstly reported to Omsk Region are marked by asterisk, new to the Asian Part of Russia – by double asterisk. The species are continuously numbered inside the catalogue.

Results

We confirmed the presence of 781 species belonging to 41 Microlepidoptera families in Omsk Region. The most numerous is Tortricidae family represented by 256 species (Table 1), then Crambidae (94 species), Gelechiidae (70), Pyralidae (66), Pterophoridae (44), Depressariidae (32), Gracillariidae (29), Tineidae (25), Elachistidae (14), Adelidae and Elachistidae (8 species in each family), Yponomeutidae, Ypsolophidae, Ethmiidae and Cosmopterigidae (7 species in each family), Scythrididae and Oecophoridae (6 species in each family), Eriocraniidae (4), Nepticulidae, Momphidae and Epermeniidae (3 species in each family), Prodoxidae, Glyphipterigidae, Lyonetiidae and Choreutidae (2 species in each family), Opostegidae, Incurvariidae, Roeslerstammiidae, Argyresthiidae, Plutelliidae, Acrolepiidae, Bedelliidae, Parametriotidae, Chimabachidae, Cryptolechiidae, Batrachedridae, Blastobasidae, Autostichidae, Galacticidae (1 species in each family).

Table 1. Taxonomic diversity of Microlepidoptera families in the Omsk Region (in systematic order)

№	Families	Species	№	Families	Species
1	Eriocraniidae	4	22	Elachistidae	14
2	Nepticulidae	3	23	Parametriotidae	1
3	Opostegidae	1	24	Scythrididae	6
4	Adelidae	8	25	Chimabachidae	1
5	Prodoxidae	2	26	Cryptolechiidae	1
6	Incurvariidae	1	27	Oecophoridae	6
7	Psychidae	7	28	Batrachedridae	1
8	Tineidae	25	29	Coleophoridae	56
9	Roeslerstammiidae	1	30	Momphidae	3
10	Bucculatricidae	5	31	Blastobasidae	1
11	Gracillariidae	29	32	Autostichidae	1
12	Yponomeutidae	7	33	Cosmopterigidae	7
13	Argyresthiidae	1	34	Gelechiidae	70
14	Plutelliidae	1	35	Pterophoridae	44
15	Acrolepiidae	1	36	Epermeniidae	3
16	Glyphipterigidae	2	37	Choreutidae	2
17	Ypsolophidae	7	38	Galacticidae	1
18	Lyonetiidae	2	39	Tortricidae	256
19	Bedelliidae	1	40	Pyralidae	66
20	Ethmiidae	7	41	Crambidae	94
21	Depressariidae	32		Total	781

Below is the list of data localities presented in alphabetical order with geographical coordinates. The serial number of each locality corresponds to the number on the map (Fig. 2).

1. 2624 km – Lybinsky district, rail station 2624 km., 4 km SW of Mokshino vill., 55°19'19.18"N, 72°16'10.43"E;
2. Abakshikha – Bolsheukovsky district, 39 km NW of Bolshiye Uki vill., Abakshikha boundary, 57°16'18.59"N, 72°19'55.78"E;
3. Achair – Omsky district, Achair vill. vicinities, 54°38'50.52"N, 73°54'14.31"E;
4. Aksenovka – Gor`kovsky district, 3 km NE of Aksyonovka vill., 55°28'37.94"N, 74°1'27.19"E;
5. Alabota – Russko-Polyansky district, Alabota vill., lake Kumdykol', 53°58'28.24"N, 73°45'1.22"E;
6. Amrinskaya Balka – Moskalensky district, 6 km SW of Gvozdevka vill., Amrinskaya Balka, 54°32'23.76"N, 71°47'43.02"E;
7. Ataichye – Cherlacksky district, 9 km NE of Dzhartargul' vill., Kurumbel'skaya steppe, lake Ataichye, 54°27'14.64"N, 75°40'0.39"E;
8. Atak – Tarsky district, Atak vill., 56°48'24"N, 74°38'36"E;
9. Atmas – Cherlacksky district, 2 km N of Malyi Atmas vill., river Irtysh, 54°0'48.74"N, 74°56'39.91"E (Fig. 7);
10. Atrachi – Tyukalinsky district, 4 km SW of Atrachi vill., 55°55'21.66"N, 71°58'3.72"E;
11. Basly – Bolsheukovsky district, 15 km SE of Basly vill., 56°56'42"N, 72°57'24"E;
12. Berezka – Isil`kul`sky district, 2 km NE of child camping "Berezka", 55°05'30"N, 71°18'10"E;
13. Berezovka – Azovsky district, Berezovka vill. vicinities 54°47'52.81"N, 73°4'0.91"E;
14. Bogdanovka – Novovarshavsky district, 8 km SE of Novovarshavka vill., 3 km NE of Bogdanovka vill., river Irtysh, 54°06'32.4"N, 74°48'55.2"E;
15. Bolshiye Murly – Bolsherechensky district, Bolshiye Murly vill. vicinities, 55°56'7.88"N, 74°33'50.56"E;
16. Bolshiye Uki – Bolsheukovsky district, Bolshiye Uki vill., 56°55'37"N, 72°37'37"E;
17. Boyevoye – Isil`kulsy district, Boyevoye vill., 54°55'58.91"N, 71°26'32.83"E;
18. Buzan – Russko-Polyansky district, 2 km SE of Buzan vill., 53°54'40"N, 73°57'31"E (Fig. 8);
19. Cherlack – Cherlacksky district, Cherlack vill., 54°9'1.89"N, 74°48'54.39"E;
20. Cherlack Station – Cherlacksky district, Cherlack rail station, 53°52'59.37"N, 75°5'44.21"E;
21. Danilovo – Muromtsevsky district, 3 km E of Kurganka vill., lake Danilovo, 56°25'45.27"N, 75°51'53.08"E;
22. Davydovka – Omsky district, 2 km N of Davydovka vill., 55°11'14"N, 73°29'47"E;
23. Ebeity – Moskalensky district, 6 km W of Gvozdevka vill., lake Ebeity, 54°35'27.89"N, 71°47'5.37"E;

24. Elizavetinka – Cherlacksy district, 3 km N of Elizavetinka vill., 54°17'37.00"N, 74°39'57.00"E;
25. Elnichnoye – Sedelnikovsky district, 1 km S of Elnichnoye vill., river Ui, 56°54'38.46"N, 76° 9'32.94"E;
26. Ermak – Novovarshevsky district, Ermak vill., 53°56'33.01"N, 75° 0'50.49"E;
27. Gulyai Pole – Krutinsky district, 44 km NW of Krutinka vill., 5 km SW of Gulyai Pole vill., 56°13'30.08"N, 70°53'44.58"E;
28. Ignatovo – Kormilovsky district, Ignatovo vill., 55°03'53.00"N, 74°11'38.00"E;
29. Isilkul' – Isil'kul'sky district, Isil'kul' town, 54°54'52.55"N, 71°15'46.01"E;
30. Kabanye – Krutinsky district, 1 km N of Kabanye vill., 56° 9'33.51"N, 71°29'40.59"E;
31. Kalachiki – Krutinsky district, Kalachiki vill., 56° 3'22.25"N, 71°38'15.23"E;
32. Kamyshino – Okoneshnikovsky district, 4,5 km NW of Kamyshino vill., 54°43'35.33"N, 74°50'7.52"E;
33. Karaklinka – Muromtsevsky district, 5 km NE of Karaklinka vill., 56°41'53"N, 75°12'41"E;
34. Keizes – Sedelnikovsky district, 8,5 km W of Keizes vill., river Stanovaya, 56°55'13.58"N, 75°34'40,31"E;
35. Khlebodarovka – Russko-Polyansky district, 8 km SW of Khlebodarovka vill., river Tleusai, 53°42'7.53"N, 73°25'11.71"E;
36. Knyazevo – Nazyvaevsky district, Knyazevo vill., 55°20'35.76"N, 70°59'30.04"E;
37. Kordon – Isil'kul'sky district, 1 km NE of Kordon N1, 55° 6'31.88"N, 71°18'12.33"E;
38. Koshkul' – Tyukalinsky district, 0,5 km N of Novyi Koshkul' vill., 56° 0'11.34"N, 72°20'42.12"E;
39. Krasnogorka – Poltavsky district, 8 km NE of Krasnogorka vill., eastern coast of Ebeity lake, 54°35'03,4"N, 71°43'38,3"E;
40. Krasnoyarka – Omsky district, Krasnoyarka vill., 55°20'0.22"N, 73° 5'33.67"E;
41. Krasnyi Oktyabr' – Cherlacksy district, Krasnyi Oktyabr' vill., 54°06'59"N, 75°01'01"E;
42. Krasnyi Yar – Krutinsky district, 1 km W of Krasnyi Yar vill., Ir river, 56°22'53.13"N, 71° 4'2.92"E;
43. Krutye Luki – Kalatshinsky district, 1,5 km N of Krutye Luki, river Om', 55° 9'44.80"N, 74°53'2.25"E;
44. Leninsk – Okoneshnikovsky district, 4 km S of Leninsk vill., 54°29'53.56"N, 75°29'21.15"E;
45. Listvyagi – Bolsheukovsky district, Listvyagi vill., 57°14'11.26"N, 71°54'52.42"E;
46. Lyubino – Lyubinsky district, Lyubino vill., 55° 9'37.44"N, 72°42'35.25"E;
47. Maiskyi – Moskalensky district, 3,5 km NNW of Maiskyi village, 55° 8'37.13"N, 71°43'48.28"E;
48. Maryanovka – Maryanovsky district, 2 km N of Maryanovka vill., 54°59'25.29"N, 72°36'41.68"E;

Figure 2. Collecting localities of Microlepidoptera in Omsk Region. The numbers inside the circles correspond to the numbers of collection localities in the text. Dark green fill – forest zone; light green fill – forest-steppe zone; yellow fill – steppe zone.

49. Merkutly – Kolosovsky district, 1 km N of Merkutly vill., 56° 6'23.19"N, 72°57'23.23"E;
50. Mezhevnyaya – Tarsky district, 4,5 km N Mezhevnyaya vill., 57° 7'38.33"N, 74°54'37.27"E;
51. Mikhailovka – Cherlacksy district, 8 km N of Mikhailovka vill., bog Kurumbel', 54°13'26.55"N, 75°15'7.38"E;
52. Moskalenki – Moskalensky district, 6 km NE of Moskalenki vill., lake Kamyshlovskoye, 54°58'48.20"N, 72°1'20.83"E;
53. Muromtsevo – Muromtsevsky district, Muromtsevo vill. vicinities, river Tara, 56°21'55.20"N, 75°16'23.86"E;
54. Nalimovo – Nazyvaevsky district, 2,5 km NW Nalimovo vill., 55°39'23.89"N, 71°47'2.94"E (Fig. 6);
55. Nikolaevka – Cherlacksy district, 9 km SE Nikolaevka vill., 54°12'16.95"N, 75° 7'55.70"E;
56. Nizhnyaya Omka – Nizhneomsky district, Nizhnyaya Omsk vill., 55°26'22.37"N, 74°56'55.40"E;
57. Novotroitskoye – Nizhneomsky district, 5 km SE of Novotroitskoye vill., 55°45'31.89"N, 75° 8'26.04"E;
58. Novovarshavka – Novovarshavsky district, 3 km E of Novovarshavka vill., river Irtysh, 54°10'0.80"N, 74°45'24.81"E;
59. Okunevo – Muromtsevsky district, Okunevo vill., 56°26'39.43"N, 74°53'49.22"E;
60. Omsk – Omsk City, 55°1'38.96"N, 73°19'1.29"E;
61. Orekhovo – Ust-Ishimsky district, 2 km NE of Orekhovo vill., 57°28'3.37"N, 70°53'3.34"E;
62. Orlovka – Okoneshnikovsky district, 1 km N of Orlovka vill., 54°44'34.87"N, 75°17'5.72"E;
63. Petropavlovka – Muromtsevsky district, Petropavlovka vill. vicinities, 56°24'46"N, 75°16'44"E (Figs 4, 5);
64. Podgorodka – Omsky district, 2 km SW of Podgorodka vill., 55° 8'10.38"N, 73°30'42.90"E;
65. Politotdel – Lyubinsky district, 2 km W of Politotdel vill., 55°12'36.59"N, 73° 7'25.20"E;
66. Poltavka – Poltavsky district, Poltavka vill., 54°22'0.17"N, 71°45'21.28"E;
67. Pospelovo – Bolsheukovsky district, 10 km S of Bolshiye Uki, 5 km W of Pospelovo vill., 56°51'17.14"N, 72°42'12.43"E;
68. Presnovka – Okoneshnikovsky district, Presnovka vill. vicinities, 54°48'0.94"N, 75°17'7.60"E;
69. Russkaya Polyana – Russko-Polyansky district, Russkaya Polyana vill., Park Yubileynyi, 53°46'29.60"N, 73°51'53.91"E;
70. Samsonovo – Tarsky district, 4 km N of Samsonovo vill., 57°0'47.38"N, 74°19'49.44"E;
71. Scholacksor – Cherlacksy district, 10 km SE of Preobrazhenka vill., lake Sholacksor, 54°16'21.24"N, 75°14'42.18"E;

72. Sedelnikovo – Sedelnikovskiy district, 2 km N of Sedelnikovo vill., 56°58'22.33"N, 75°17'13.09"E;
73. Serebryanoye – Gorkovskiy district, Serebryanoye vill. vicinities, river Irtysh, 55°43'0.29"N, 74°20'21.88"E;
74. Solntsevka – Isil`kulskiy district, Solntsevka vill. vic., 55° 0'19.39"N, 71°17'41.29"E;
75. Solyanoye – Cherlackskiy district, Solyanoye vill., Solyanoye vill., 54°21'4.40"N, 74°38'2.06"E;
76. Syropyatskoye – Kormilovskiy district, 5 km NE of Syropyatskoye vill., 55°5'25.44"N, 73°55'29.82"E;
77. Tatarka – Cherlackskiy district, 2 km N of Tatarka vill., 53°58'58.47"N, 75°2'1.22"E;
78. Timshinyakovo – Tarskiy district, 0,5 km N of Timshinyakovo vill., 56°57'8.97"N, 74°25'49.51"E;
79. Ul`zhai – Cherlackskiy district, 6 km SE of Nikolaevka vill., lake Ul`zhai, 54°13'48.02"N, 75° 6'51.61"E;
80. Urusovo – Sargatskiy district, 4 km SE of Urusovo vill., 55°37'46"N, 73°20'07"E;
81. Ust-Ishim – Ust-Ishimskiy district, 5,5 km NW of Ust-Ishim vill., 57°43'01,17"N", 71°03'57,93"E (Fig. 3);
82. Verkhneilyinka – Cherlackskiy district, 2 km NW of Verkhneilyinka vill., 54°33'30.61"N, 74°14'26.02"E;
83. Yakovlevka – Bolsheukovskiy district, 28 km NW of Bolshiye Uki vill., Yakovlevka boundary, river Tevriz, 57°10'38.79"N, 72°25'16.34"E;
84. Yuryevo – Kormilovskiy district, 3 km NW of Yuryevo village, Tarbuga river, 55°10'9.30"N, 74°9'39.39"E.

Figure 3. Sphagnum swamp in the North-West of the forest zone, Ust-Ishimskiy district, 5,5 km NW of Ust-Ishim vill., 7.VI.2018, photo by S.A. Knyazev.

Figure 4. Pine Forest in the forest zone, Muromtsevsky district, Petropavlovka vill. vicinity, 26.V.2009, photo by S.A. Knyazev.

Figure 5. Mixed forest in the forest zone, Petropavlovka vill. vicinity, 4.X.2008, photo by S.A. Knyazev.

Figure 6. Meadow near the Birch forest in the forest-steppe zone, Nazyvaevsky district, 2,5 km NW Nalimovo vill., 20.VII.2019, photo by S.A. Knyazev.

Figure 7. Floodplain of the Irtysh river on the South of the forest-steppe zone, Cherlaksy district, 2 km N of Malyi Atmas vill., 7.VII.2011, photo by S.A. Knyazev.

Figure 8. Steppe on the South of Omsk Region, Russko-Polyansky district, 2 km SE of Buzan vill., 22.VI.2018, photo by S.A. Knyazev.

List of species

Eriocraniidae

1. *Eriocrania sangii* (Wood, 1891) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Keizes, Davydovka. FP: IV-V.
2. *Eriocrania semipurpurella* (Stephens, 1835) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Timshinyakovo, Gulyai Pole. FP: IV.
3. *Eriocrania sparrmannella* (Bosc, 1791) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Keizes, Davydovka. FP: IV-V.
4. *Eriocrania unimaculella* (Zetterstedt, 1839) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Gulyai Pole. FP: IV.

Nepticulidae

5. *Stigmella obliquella* (Heinemann, 1862) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
6. *Stigmella trimaculella* (Haworth, 1828) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
7. **Fomoria weaveri* (Stainton, 1855) – LOC: Ust-Ishim. FP: V-VI. First record to West Siberia. The species was identified by the leaf mine on *Vaccinium vitis-idaea*.

Opostegidae

8. *Opostega salaciella* (Treitschke, 1833) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Samsonovo. FP: VII.

Adelidae

Adelinae

9. *Nemophora amatella* (Staudinger, 1892) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Listvyagi, Sedelnikovo, Petropavlovka. FP: VI-VII.
10. *Nemophora basella* (Eversmann, 1844) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Krasnyi Oktyabr'; Cherlack station. FP: VI.
11. *Nemophora bellela* (Walker, 1863) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
12. *Nemophora dumerilella* (Duponchel, 1839) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Amrinskaya Balka. FP: VIII.
13. *Adela cuprella* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Davydovka, Omsk. FP: IV-V.

Nematopogoninae

14. *Nematopogon pilella* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Podgorodka, Davydovka. FP: V-VI.
15. *Nematopogon swammerdamella* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Atak. FP: V.
16. *Cauchas florella* (Staudinger, 1871) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Buzan. FP: V.

Prodoxidae

17. *Lampronia capitella* (Clerck, 1759) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Bolshiye Uki. FP: V-VI.

18. *Lampronia fuscata* (Tengström, 1848) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Davydovka. FP: V.

Incurvariidae

19. *Incurvaria pectinea* Haworth, 1828 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Krasnyi Oktyabr`. FP: V.

Psychidae

Narycinae

20. *Dahlica listrella* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Davydovka. FP: IV.

Taleporiinae

21. *Taleporia tubulosa* (Retzius, 1783) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Sedelnikovo, Omsk. FP: VI-VII.

Epichnopteriginae

22. *Rebelia perlucidella* (Bruand, 1853) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Davydovka, Ul`zhai. FP: V-VI.

Oiketicinae

23. *Canephora hirsuta* (Poda, 1761) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Okunevo, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Podgorodka, Davydovka, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Atmos. FP: VI-VII. Fig. 9.
24. *Ptilocephala plumifera* (Ochsenheimer, 1810) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Solyanoye. FP: V.
25. *Phalacropterix graslinella* (Boisduval, 1852) REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Gulyai Pole. FP: V-VI.
26. *Sterrhopterix fusca* (Haworth, 1809) REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Yakovlevka, Samsonovo, Timshinyakovo, Sedelnikovo, Okunevo, Gulyai Pole, Koshkul`, Nalimovo, Maiskiy, Krasnoyarka. FP: V-VII.

Tineidae

Mirmecozelinae

27. *Myrmecozela lutosella* (Eversmann, 1844) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Ataichye, Buzan. FP: VI.

28. *Myrmecozela ochraceella* (Tengström, 1848) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Nikolaevka, Maisky. FP: VI.
29. *Ateliotum hungaricellum* Zeller, 1839 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Buzan. FP: VIII.
30. *Haplotinea insectella* (Fabricius, 1794) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI-VII.
31. *Cephimallota praetoriella* (Christoph, 1872) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk, Amrinskaya Balka, Buzan. FP: V-VII.

Scardiinae

32. *Scardia boletella* (Fabricius, 1794) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Samsonovo, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Davydovka, Omsk. FP: VI-VIII. Fig. 10.
33. *Morophaga choragella* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Samsonovo, Gulyai Pole, Davydovka, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Russkaya Polyana. FP: VI-VII.

Nemapogoninae

34. *Triaxomera fulvimitrella* (Sodoffsky, 1830) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Davydovka. FP: VI.
35. *Archinemapogon yildizae* Koçak, 1981 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Davydovka, Omsk, Buzan. FP: V-VII.
36. *Nemapogon cloacella* (Haworth, 1828) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Podgorodka. FP: VI.
37. *Nemapogon picarella* (Clerck, 1759) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Petropavlovka, Podgorodka, Omsk, Nikolaevka, Atmos, Buzan. FP: V-VII.
38. *Nemapogon variatella* (Clemens, 1859) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr'. FP: VI-VIII.

Tineinae

39. *Trichophaga tapetzella* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk, Amrinskaya Balka, Nikolaevka. FP: VI.
40. *Tineola bisselliella* (Hummel, 1823) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk. FP: I-XII.
41. *Tinea bothniella* Svensson, 1953 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
42. *Tinea columbariella* Wocke, 1877 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk, Bogdanovka. FP: V-VI.
43. *Tinea omichlopis* Meyrick, 1928 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Atmos, Buzan. FP: VIII.

44. *Tinea pelliionella* Linnaeus, 1758 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk. FP: III.
45. *Niditinea striolella* (Matsumura, 1931) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk. FP: IV-VI.
46. *Monopis crocicapitella* (Clemens, 1859) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI-VII.
47. *Monopis laevigella* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Okunevo, Davydovka. FP: V-VI.
48. *Monopis monachella* (Hübner, 1796) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Bolshiye Uki, Gulyai Pole, Atrachi, Davydovka, Omsk, Yuryevo, Nikolaevka, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmas, Novovarshavka, Bogdanovka. FP: V-IX.
49. *Monopis obviella* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Podgorodka, Omsk. FP: VI-VII.
50. *Monopis spilotella* (Tengström, 1848) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Sedelnikovo. FP: VI-VII.
51. *Monopis weaverella* (Scott, 1858) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.

Figure 9. *Canephora hirsuta*, Davydovka, ex larva, 8.VI.2014, photo by S.A. Knyazev.

Figure 10. *Scardia boletella*, larva, Davydovka, 11.IV.2020, photo by S.A. Knyazev.

Roeslerstammiidae

52. *Roeslerstammia erxebella* (Fabricius, 1787) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Samsonovo. FP: VI.

Bucculatricidae

53. *Bucculatrix artemisiella* Herrich-Schäffer, 1855 – REF: Baryshnikova 2014; Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Atmas, Buzan. FP: V-IX.
54. *Bucculatrix cristatella* (Zeller, 1839) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2019; Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Buzan. FP: V-VI.
55. *Bucculatrix humiliella* Herrich-Schäffer, 1855 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Karaklinka. FP: V.
56. *Bucculatrix maritima* Stainton, 1851 – REF: Baryshnikova 2014; Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
57. *Bucculatrix ulmella* Zeller, 1848 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Davydovka. FP: VI.

Gracillariidae

Ornixolinae

58. *Ornixola caudulatella* (Zeller, 1839) – REF: Baryshnikova 2014; Knyazev et al. 2018. LOC: Omsk. FP: VII.
59. *Parectopa ononidis* (Zeller, 1839) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2018. LOC: Davydovka. FP: VI.
60. *Micrurapteryx caraganella* (Hering, 1957) – REF: Kirichenko et al. 2016; Knyazev et al. 2018. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI-VII.

Gracillariinae

61. *Gracillaria syringella* (Fabricius, 1794) – REF: Baryshnikova 2014; Knyazev et al. 2018. LOC: Bolshiye Murly. FP: VI.
62. *Caloptilia betulicola* (M.Hering, 1928) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2018. LOC: Podgorodka, Davydovka. FP: IV-V.
63. *Caloptilia elongella* (Linnaeus, 1761) – REF: Baryshnikova 2014; Knyazev et al. 2018. LOC: Berezka, Davydovka. FP: V, X.
64. *Caloptilia populetorum* (Zeller, 1839) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2018. LOC: Gulyai Pole. FP: IX.
65. *Caloptilia stigmatella* (Fabricius, 1781) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2018. LOC: Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Podgorodka, Davydovka, Omsk, Tatarka. FP: IV-X.
66. *Eupsilapteryx auroguttella* (Stephens, 1835) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2018. LOC: Samsonovo. FP: VII.
67. *Calybites phasianipennella* (Hübner, 1813) – REF: Baryshnikova 2014; Knyazev et al. 2018. LOC: Davydovka, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Tatarka. FP: IV-V.

Parornichinae

68. *Parornix betulae* (Stainton, 1854) – REF: Baryshnikova 2014; Knyazev et al. 2018. LOC: Samsonovo, Gulyai Pole, Omsk. FP: VI.

Lithocolletinae

69. *Phyllonorycter agilella* (Zeller, 1846) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2018. LOC: Omsk. FP: VII.
70. *Phyllonorycter apparella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2018. LOC: Yakovlevka, Samsonovo, Omsk, Elizavetinka, Tatarka. FP: VI-VII.
71. *Phyllonorycter cavella* (Zeller, 1846) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2018. LOC: Muromtsevo. FP: V.
72. *Phyllonorycter comparella* (Duponchel, 1843) – REF: Kirichenko et al. 2017; Knyazev et al. 2018. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.

73. *Phyllonorycter corylifoliella* (Hübner, 1796) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2018. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
74. *Phyllonorycter insignitella* (Zeller, 1846) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2018. LOC: Gulyai Pole. FP: V.
75. *Phyllonorycter issikii* (Kumata, 1963) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2018. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Yakovlevka, Podgorodka, Omsk. FP: VII-X.
76. *Phyllonorycter klemannella* (Fabricius, 1781) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2018. LOC: Omsk. FP: VII.
77. *Phyllonorycter medicaginella* (Gerasimov, 1930) – REF: Kirichenko et al. 2017; Knyazev et al. 2018. LOC: Omsk. FP: VII.
78. *Phyllonorycter pastorella* (Zeller, 1846) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2018. LOC: Omsk, Elizavetinka, Tatarka. FP: VII-X.
79. *Phyllonorycter populifoliella* (Treitschke, 1833) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2018. LOC: Omsk. FP: VII-X.
80. *Phyllonorycter schreberella* (Fabricius, 1781) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2018. LOC: Omsk. FP: VII-X.
81. *Phyllonorycter sorbi* (Frey, 1855) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2018. LOC: Omsk. FP: VII.
82. *Phyllonorycter ulmifoliella* (Hübner, 1817) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2018. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI-VII.

Acrocercopinae

83. *Sauterina hofmanniella* (Schleich, 1867) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2019. LOC: Petropavlovka. FP: VI.
84. *Acrocercops brongiardella* (Fabricius, 1798) – REF: Chursina et al. 2016; Knyazev et al. 2018. LOC: Omsk. FP: VII-X, IV.

Phyllocnistinae

85. *Phyllocnistis extrematrix* Martynova, 1955 – REF: Knyazev et al. 2018. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
86. *Phyllocnistis labyrinthella* (Bjerkander, 1790) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2018. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.

Yponomeutidae

Yponomeutinae

87. *Yponomeuta evonymella* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Samsonovo, Petropavlovka, Davydovka, Omsk, Atmos. FP: VI-VIII.

88. *Yponomeuta vigintipunctatus* (Retzius, 1783) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Petropavlovka, Atrachi. FP: VI-VIII.
89. *Euhyponomeutoides ribesiellus* (Joannis, 1900) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Petropavlovka, Timshinyakovo. FP: IV-VI.
90. *Kessleria fasciapennella* (Stainton, 1849) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Keizes, Gulyai Pole. FP: IV.
91. *Swammerdamia caesiella* (Hübner, 1796) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021; OC: Davydovka. FP: VI.
92. *Swammerdamia glaucella* Junnilainen, 2001 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Serebryanoye. FP: VI.
93. *Cedestis gysseleniella* Zeller, 1839 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.

Argyresthiidae

94. *Argyresthia brockeella* (Hübner, 1813) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Berezka, Davydovka, Omsk. FP: VII-VIII.

Plutellidae

95. *Plutella xylostella* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Yakovlevka, Bolshiye Uki, Atak, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Merkutly, Davydovka, Omsk, Berezovka, Verkhneilyinka, Ul'zhai, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos, Tatarka, Buzan. FP: V-IX.

Acrolepiidae

96. *Acrolepiopsis assectella* (Zeller, 1839) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Tatarka. FP: IV.

Glyphipterigidae

97. *Glyphipterix equitella* (Scopoli, 1763) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Ust-Ishim. FP: VI.
98. *Glyphipterix haworthana* (Stephens, 1834) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Ust-Ishim. FP: VI.

Ypsolophidae

Ypsolophinae

99. *Ypsolopha asperella* (Linnaeus, 1761) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Timshinyakovo, Keizes, Podgorodka, Davydovka, Omsk, Atmos. FP: IV-V, IX-X.

100. *Ypsolopha falcella* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Podgorodka. FP: VIII.
101. *Ypsolopha instabilella* (Mann, 1866) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Buzan, Tatarka. FP: IX.
102. *Ypsolopha nemorella* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Podgorodka. FP: VII.
103. *Ypsolopha parenthesesella* (Linnaeus, 1761) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Keizes, Petropavlovka. FP: IX.
104. *Ypsolopha scabrella* (Linnaeus, 1761) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Petropavlovka. FP: IX.

Ochsenheimerinae

105. *Ochsenheimeria urella* Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1842 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Krasnyi Oktyabr'. FP: V.

Lyonetiidae

Lyonetiinae

106. *Lyonetia clerkella* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Mezhevnaya. FP: VI-X.
107. *Lyonetia ledi* Wocke, 1859 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Podgorodka. FP: VII.

Bedelliidae

108. *Bedellia somnulentella* (Zeller, 1847) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Davydovka, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos, Buzan. FP: VIII-X.

Ethmiidae

109. *Ethmia aurifluella* (Hübner, 1810) – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Ebeity. FP: V.
110. *Ethmia bipunctella* (Fabricius, 1775) – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Podgorodka, Omsk, Bogdanovka, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos, Buzan. FP: V-VIII.
111. *Ethmia cirrhocnemis* (Lederer, 1872) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Serebryanoye, Omsk. FP: V-VI.
112. *Ethmia dodecea* (Haworth, 1828) – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Ebeity. FP: VII.
113. *Ethmia pusiella* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Davydovka, Kamyshino, Ebeity, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos. FP: V.

114. *Ethmia pyrausta* (Pallas, 1771) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2015. LOC: Novotroit-skoye, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Cherlack. FP: IV-V.
115. *Ethmia quadrillella* (Goeze, 1783) – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Serebryanoye, Podgorodka, Omsk. FP: V-VI.

Depressariidae

Depressariinae

116. *Semioscopsis avellanella* (Hübner, 1793) – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Samsonovo, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Davydovka. FP: IV-V. Fig. 11.
117. *Semioscopsis oculella* (Thunberg, 1794) – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Davydovka, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos, Tatarka. FP: IV-V. Fig. 12.
118. *Semioscopsis steinkellneriana* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Samsonovo, Atak, Petropavlovka. FP: IV-V.
119. *Semioscopsis strigulana* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Yakovlevka, Bolshiye Uki, Pospelovo, Samsonovo, Petropavlovka, Davydovka. FP: VII.
120. *Exaeretia allisella* Stainton, 1849 – REF: Knyazev et al. 2015. LOC: Samsonovo, Gulyai Pole. FP: VIII.
121. *Exaeretia ciniflonella* (Lienig & Zeller, 1846) – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Yakovlevka, Samsonovo, Timshinyakovo, Mezhevnyaya, Karaklinka, Petropavlovka, Podgorodka, Davydovka. FP: IV-V, VIII-X. Fig. 13.
122. *Exaeretia lepidella* (Christoph, 1872) – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Urusovo, Davydovka, Ebeity, Krasnyi Oktyabr'. FP: V-VI.
123. *Exaeretia praeustella* (Rebel, 1917) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2015. LOC: Ebeity. FP: IX.
124. *Agonopterix alstromeriana* (Clerck, 1759) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2019. LOC: Ust-Ishim. FP: IX.
125. *Agonopterix angelicella* (Hübner, 1813) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2015. LOC: Samsonovo. FP: VIII.
126. *Agonopterix arenella* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Petropavlovka, Davydovka. FP: IV-VI, IX-X. Fig. 14.
127. *Agonopterix ciliella* (Stainton, 1849) – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Pospelovo, Bolshiye Uki, Samsonovo, Keizes, Mezhevnyaya, Petropavlovka, Kalachiki, Davydovka. FP: IV-V, VIII-X.
128. *Agonopterix heracliana* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Yakovlevka, Bolshiye Uki, Petropavlovka, Omsk. FP: IV-V, VIII-X.
129. *Agonopterix hypericella* (Hübner, 1817) – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Atak. FP: IV-V, VIII-X.
130. *Agonopterix medelichensis* Buchner, 2015 – REF: Lvovsky, Knyazev 2013; Lvovsky, Knyazev 2016. LOC: Krasnyi Oktyabr', Tatarka. FP: IV-V.

Figure 11. *Semioscopsis avellanella*, Davydovka, 11.IV.2020, photo by S.A. Knyazev.

Figure 12. *Semioscopsis oculella*, Davydovka, 11.IV.2020, photo by S.A. Knyazev.

Figure 13. *Exaeretia ciniflonella*, Yakovlevka, overwintering moth under the tree bark, 19.I.2018, photo by S.A. Knyazev.

Figure 14. *Agonopterix arenella*, Petropavlovka, 4.X.2008, photo by S.A. Knyazev.

131. *Agonopterix melancholica* (Rebel, 1917) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2015. LOC: Ebeity. FP: VIII.
132. *Agonopterix multiplicella* (Erschoff, 1877) – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Petropavlovka, Omsk. FP: IV-V, VIII-X.
133. *Agonopterix ocellana* (Fabricius, 1775) – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Yakovlevka, Bolshiye Uki, Atak, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Novotroit-skoye, Davydovka, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos. FP: IV-V, VIII-X.
134. *Agonopterix pallorella* (Zeller, 1839) – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Atrachi, Davydovka, Krasnyi Oktyabr'. FP: IV-V, VIII-X.
135. *Agonopterix propinquella* (Treitschke, 1835) – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Politotdel, Podgorodka, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Tatarka. FP: IV-V, VIII-X.
136. ***Agonopterix purpurea* (Haworth, 1811) – LOC: Timshinyakovo. FP: IV.
137. *Agonopterix subtakamukui* Lvovsky, 1998 – REF: Knyazev et al. 2017. LOC: Gulyai Pole. FP: IX.
138. *Depressaria hystricella* Möschler, 1860 – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Pokrovo-Irtyshskoye, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Tatarka. FP: IV-V, VIII-X.
139. *Depressaria chaerophylli* Zeller, 1839 – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Bolshiye Uki. FP: IV-V, VIII-X.
140. *Depressaria depressana* (Fabricius, 1775) – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Omsk, Atmos. FP: IV-V, VIII-X.
141. *Depressaria libanotidella* Schläger, 1849 – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Petropavlovka, Davydovka. FP: IV-V, VIII-X.
142. *Depressaria olerella* Zeller, 1854 – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Petropavlovka. FP: IV-V, VIII-X.
143. *Depressaria pimpinellae* Zeller, 1839 – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Atak, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Davydovka, Omsk. FP: IV-V, VIII-X.
144. *Depressaria radiella* (Goeze, 1783) – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Krasnyi Oktyabr', Tatarka. FP: IV-V, VIII-X.
145. *Depressaria rubricella* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Krasnyi Oktyabr'. FP: IV-V, VIII-X.
146. *Depressaria sibirica* Lvovsky, 1981 – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Petropavlovka, Davydovka, Buzan. FP: IV-V, VIII-X.
147. *Depressaria sordidatella* Tengström, 1848 – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Krasnyi Oktyabr', Buzan. FP: IV-V, VIII-X.

Elachistidae

148. *Mendesia farinella* (Thunberg, 1794) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
149. *Elachista anserinella* Zeller, 1839 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Podgorodka, Davydovka, Bogdanovka, Buzan. FP: V-VI.

150. *Elachista fasciola* Parenti, 1983 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Davydovka, Ebeity. FP: V-VI.
151. *Elachista humilis* Zeller, 1850 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Koshkul'. FP: VI.
152. *Elachista littoricola* Le Marchand, 1938 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Solntsevka. FP: VI.
153. *Elachista maculicerusella* Bruand, 1859 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Nikolaevka, Atmos. FP: VI-VIII.
154. *Elachista pollutella* Duponchel, 1843 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Ul'zhai, Krasnogorka, Buzan. FP: V-VI.
155. *Elachista pullicomella* Zeller, 1839 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Buzan. FP: VI.
156. *Elachista rudectella* Stainton, 1851 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk, Buzan. FP: V-VI.
157. *Elachista spumella* Caradja, 1920 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Ul'zhai, Buzan. FP: VI.
158. *Elachista subalbidella* Schläger, 1847 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Davydovka. FP: VI.
159. *Biselachista albidella* (Nylander, 1848) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Ataihye, Nikolaevka. FP: VI.
160. *Biselachista utonella* (Frey, 1856) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI-VII.
161. *Cosmiotes freyerella* (Hübner, 1825) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI-VII.

Parametriotidae

162. *Heinemannia laspeyrella* (Hübner, 1796) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Petropavlovka. FP: VI.

Scythrididae

163. *Scythris clavella* (Zeller, 1855) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Leninsk, Sholacksor. FP: VI-VII.
164. *Scythris flavilaterella* (Fuchs, 1886) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Sedelnikovo, Gulyai Pole. FP: VI-VII.
165. *Scythris mikkolai* Sinev, 1993 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk, Atmos. FP: VII.
166. *Scythris minorella* Sinev, 2001 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Ataihye. FP: VI.
167. *Scythris obscurella* (Scopoli, 1763) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Samsonovo, Sedelnikovo, Gulyai Pole. FP: VI-VII.

168. *Scythris sinensis* (R.Felder et Rogenhofer, 1875) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk, Krutye Luki. FP: VI.

Chimabachidae

169. *Dasystema salicella* (Hübner, 1796) – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Yakovlevka, Davydovka. FP: IV-V.

Cryptolechiidae

170. *Hypercallia citrinalis* (Scopoli, 1763) – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Gulyai Pole. FP: VII-VIII.

Oecophoridae

Oecophorinae

171. *Bisigna procerella* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Davydovka. FP: VII.
172. *Epicallima formosella* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Omsk. FP: VII.
173. *Denisia similella* (Hübner, 1796) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2017. LOC: Samsonovo. FP: VI.
174. *Denisia stipella* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Davydovka, Omsk. FP: VI-VII.

Pleurotinae

175. *Pleurota aorsella* Christoph, 1872 – REF: Knyazev et al. 2019. LOC: Buzan. FP: VI.
176. *Pleurota malatya* Back, 1973 – REF: Knyazev et al. 2015. LOC: Gulyai Pole. FP: VI.

Batrachedridae

177. *Batrachedra praeangusta* (Haworth, 1828) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk. FP: VII.

Coleophoridae

178. *Casas albella* (Thunberg, 1788) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2016. LOC: Davydovka. FP: VI.

179. *Haploptilia prunifoliae* (Doets, 1944) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk, Novovarshevka. FP: VI.
180. *Quadratia fuscocuprella* (Herrich-Schaffer, 1855) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2016. LOC: Davydovka. FP: VI.
181. *Kasyfia orbitella* (Zeller, 1849) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2016. LOC: Davydovka. FP: VI.
182. *Helopharea ledi* (Stainton, 1860) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Gulyai Pole. FP: VI.
183. *Agapalsa vacciniella* (Herrich-Schaffer, 1861) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2016. LOC: Davydovka. FP: VI.
184. *Orghidania gryphipennella* (Hübner, 1796) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
185. *Chnoocera botaurella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1861) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Maryanovka. FP: VII.
186. *Bourgogneja pennella* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Atmos. FP: VI.
187. *Helvalbia lineolea* (Haworth, 1828) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2016. LOC: Davydovka. FP: VI.
188. *Oedicaula serinipennella* (Christoph, 1872) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2012; Anikin and Knyazev 2016. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
189. *Coleophora albidella* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Gulyai Pole. FP: VI.
190. *Coleophora betulella* Heinemann & Wocke, 1877 – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Davydovka, Omsk. FP: VI.
191. *Coleophora currucipennella* Zeller, 1839 – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Gulyai Pole. FP: VI.
192. *Coleophora ibipennella* Zeller, 1849 – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2016. LOC: Sedelnikovo. FP: VII.
193. *Coleophora zelleriella* Heinemann, 1854 – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Atmos. FP: VI.
194. *Orthographis* sp. – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2012; Anikin and Knyazev 2016. LOC: Davydovka. FP: VII.
195. *Phagolamia virgatella* (Zeller, 1849) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2012; Anikin and Knyazev 2016. LOC: Atmos. FP: VII.
196. *Damophila alcyonipennella* (Kollar, 1832) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2012; Anikin and Knyazev 2016; Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Timshinyakovo, Gulyai Pole, Buzan. FP: V-VIII.
197. *Damophila deauratella* (Lienig et Zeller, 1846) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2012; Anikin and Knyazev 2016; Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Orekhovo, Bolshiye Uki, Samsonovo, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Maiskyi, Davydovka, Omsk. FP: VI-VIII.

198. *Damophila trifolii* Curtis, 1832 – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2012; Anikin and Knyazev 2016; Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Ataichye, Atmos. FP: VI-VII.
199. *Eupista ornatipennella* (Hübner, 1796) – REF: Anikin 2019; Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Maiskiy, Amrinskaya Balka. FP: VI.
200. *Eupista samarensis* Anikin, 2001 – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Atmos. FP: VII.
201. *Multicoloria cartilaginella* (Christoph, 1872) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Atmos. FP: VI.
202. *Multicoloria conspicuella* (Zeller, 1849) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2016. LOC: Ataichye. FP: VI.
203. *Multicoloria cracella* (Vallot, 1835) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Atmos. FP: VI.
204. *Multicoloria ditella* (Zeller, 1849) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2012; Anikin and Knyazev 2016. LOC: Ataichye, Buzan. FP: VI.
205. *Multicoloria vibicigerella* (Zeller, 1839) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2016; Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Podgorodka, Davydovka, Nikolae-vka, Atmos, Buzan. FP: V-VII.
206. *Multicoloria vicinella* (Zeller, 1849) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2012; Anikin and Knyazev 2016. LOC: Atmos. FP: VII.
207. *Apista callipelpa* Falkovitsh, 1979 – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2016. LOC: Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr`. FP: V.
208. *Apista dignella* (Toll, 1961) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2012; Anikin and Knyazev 2016. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
209. *Apista gallipennella* (Hübner, 1796) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2016; Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Davydovka. FP: VI.
210. *Perygra alticolella* (Zeller, 1849) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2012; Anikin and Knyazev 2016. LOC: Bogdanovka. FP: V.
211. *Perygra adjunctella* (Hodgkinson, 1882) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2012; Anikin and Knyazev 2016; Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Davydovka, Omsk, Buzan. FP: V-VI.
212. *Ecebalia gaviaepennella* (Toll, 1952) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2016; Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Atrachi, Verkhneilyinka, Buzan. FP: VIII-IX.
213. *Ecebalia proterella* (Wilkinson et Tabell, 2016) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Buzan. FP: VIII.
214. *Ecebalia saxicolella* (Duponchel, 1843) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Buzan. FP: VIII.
215. *Ecebalia therinella* (Tengström, 1848) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2012; Anikin and Knyazev 2016. LOC: Politotdel. FP: VIII.
216. *Ecebalia vestianella* (Linnaenus, 1758) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2012; Anikin and Knyazev 2016; – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk, Buzan. FP: VIII.

217. *Casignetella albicans* (Zeller, 1849) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Buzan. FP: V.
218. *Casignetella ancistrum* (Falkovitsh, 1976) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Buzan. FP: VI.
219. *Casignetella artemisicolella* (Bruand, [1855]) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2016. LOC: Samsonovo. FP: VIII.
220. *Casignetella ciconiella* (Herrich-Schaffer, 1855) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2012; Anikin and Knyazev 2016. LOC: Atmos. FP: VII.
221. *Casignetella directella* (Zeller, 1849) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Buzan. FP: VIII.
222. *Casignetella estriatella* (Li et Zheng, 1999) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2012; Anikin and Knyazev 2016. LOC: Atmos. FP: VIII.
223. *Casignetella gnaphalii* (Zeller, 1839) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2016. LOC: Omsk. FP: VIII.
224. *Casignetella granulata* (Zeller, 1849) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2012; Anikin and Knyazev 2016. LOC: Atmos. FP: VIII.
225. *Casignetella loxodon* Falkovitsh, 1993 – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2016. LOC: Davydovka. FP: VI.
226. *Casignetella nutantella* (Mühlig & Frey, 1857) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Gulyai Pole. FP: VI.
227. *Casignetella occatella* (Staudinger, 1880) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Buzan. FP: VIII.
228. *Casignetella paripennella* (Zeller, 1839) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Gulyai Pole. FP: VI.
229. *Casignetella peribenanderi* (Toll, 1943) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2016. LOC: Davydovka. FP: VI.
230. *Casignetella striatipennella* (Tengström, [1848]) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2012; Anikin and Knyazev 2016. LOC: Gulyai Pole. FP: VI.
231. *Ionescumia clypeiferella* (O.Hofmann, 1871) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2012; Anikin and Knyazev 2016. LOC: Atmos. FP: VIII.
232. *Carpochena lativittella* (Erschoff, 1877) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Buzan. FP: VIII.
233. *Carpochena binotapennella* (Duponchel, 1843) – REF: Anikin and Knyazev 2016. LOC: Omsk. FP: VII.

Momphidae

234. *Cyphophora idaei* (Zeller, 1839) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Sedelnikovo. FP: VII.
235. *Mompha glaucella* Sinev, 1986 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Omsk. FP: IV-V, IX-X.
236. *Mompha sturnipennella* (Treitschke, 1833) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Samsonovo, Gulyai Pole. FP: IV-V, IX-X.

Blastobasidae

237. *Hypatopa binotella* (Thunberg, 1794) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk, Atmos. FP: VII.

Autostichidae

238. *Deroxena venosulella* (Möschler, 1862) – REF: Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012. LOC: Ebeity, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Atmos, Buzan. FP: V-VI.

Cosmopterigidae

239. *Pancalia leuwenhoekella* (Linnaeus, 1761) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Petropavlovka. FP: VI.
240. *Cosmopterix orichalcea* Stainton, 1861 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
241. *Cosmopterix sibirica* Sinev, 1985 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Davydovka. FP: V-VI.
242. *Limnaecia phragmitella* Stainton, 1851 – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI-VII.
243. *Pyroderces argyrogrammos* (Zeller, 1847) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
244. *Eteobalea anonymella* (Riedl, 1965) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Serebryanoye, Davydovka, Omsk, Buzan. FP: VI.
245. *Eteobalea tririvella* (Staudinger, 1871) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Davydovka, Omsk, Atmos. FP: VI-VII.

Gelechiidae

Anomologinae

246. *Pyncostola bohemiella* (Nickerl, 1864) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI-VII.
247. *Metzneria aprilella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Sedelnikovo, Gulyai Pole, Davydovka, Omsk, Atmos. FP: VI-VII.
248. *Metzneria lappella* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI-VII.
249. *Metzneria metzneriella* (Stainton, 1851) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Davydovka, Omsk. FP: VI.
250. *Metzneria neuropterella* (Zeller, 1839) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Gulyai Pole, Omsk. FP: VII.

251. *Monochroa elongella* (Heinemann, 1870) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
252. *Monochroa inflexella* Svensson, 1992 – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Davydovka. FP: VI.
253. *Monochroa lutulentella* (Zeller, 1839) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Davydovka. FP: VI-VII.
254. *Monochroa nomadella* (Zeller, 1868) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
255. *Monochroa schistacea* M. Omelko et N. Omelko, 2017 – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Abakshikha, Omsk. FP: VI.
256. *Eulamprotes wilkella* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Omsk, Ul'zhai, Atmos. FP: VI-VIII.
257. *Chrysoesthia drurella* (Fabricius, 1775) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
258. *Megacraspedus longipalpella* Junnilainen, 2010 – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Atmos. FP: VI-VII.
259. *Aristotelia subericinella* (Duponchel, 1843) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Atmos. FP: VII-VIII.
260. *Xystophora pulveratella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Davydovka. FP: VI.
261. *Bryotropha purpurella* (Zetterstedt, 1839) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Davydovka. FP: VI.
262. *Bryotropha similis* (Stainton, 1854) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Samsonovo, Gulyai Pole, Berezka, Podgorodka, Davydovka, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos. FP: VI-VII.
263. *Pexicopia malvella* (Hübner, [1805]) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI-VIII.

Gelechiinae

264. *Gelechia rhombella* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Omsk, Syropyatskoye. FP: VI-VIII.
265. *Gelechia repetitrix* Meyrick, 1931 – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Atmos. FP: VI.
266. *Gelechia turpella* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Omsk, Atmos. FP: VII-VIII.
267. *Psoricoptera gibbosella* (Zeller, 1839) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Omsk. FP: IX.
268. *Psoricoptera speciosella* Teich, 1892 – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Atrachi, Syropyatskoye. FP: VIII-IX.
269. *Chionodes holosericella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Samsonovo. FP: VII.

270. *Chionodes luctuella* (Hübner, 1793) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Abakshikha. FP: VI.
271. *Chionodes lugubrella* (Fabricius, 1794) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Davydovka, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr`. FP: VI.
272. *Chionodes mongolica* Piskunov, 1979 – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
273. *Chionodes tragicella* (Heyden, 1865) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
274. *Aroga aristotelis* (Millière, [1876]) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Davydovka, Atmos. FP: VII-VIII.
275. *Aroga velocella* (Zeller, 1839) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Atmos, Buzan. FP: VII-VIII.
276. *Filatima incomptella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Atak, Davydovka. FP: V-VI.
277. *Filatima tephritidella* (Duponchel, 1844) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Krasnyi Oktyabr`. FP: V.
278. *Athrips amoenella* (Frey, 1882) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Davydovka. FP: VI.
279. *Athrips pruinosa* (Lienig et Zeller, 1846) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Sedelnikovo. FP: VII.
280. *Athrips tetrapunctella* (Thunberg, 1794) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Davydovka, Omsk. FP: V-VI.
281. *Holcophora statices* Staudinger, 1871 – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Novotroitskoye, Ebeity, Ul`zhai, Ermak, Buzan. FP: V-VIII.
282. *Cosmardia moritzella* (Treitschke, 1835) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Podgorodka, Krasnyi Oktyabr`. FP: V-X.
283. *Agonochaetia intermedia* Sattler, 1968 – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Davydovka. FP: VI.
284. *Caryocolum cassella* (Walker, 1864) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI-VII.
285. *Caryocolum fischerella* (Treitschke, 1833) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Omsk. FP: VIII.
286. *Exoteleia dodecella* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI-VII.
287. *Parachronistis albiceps* (Zeller, 1839) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
288. *Teleiodes flavimaculella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Davydovka, Omsk. FP: VI.
289. *Teleiodes vulgella* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI-VIII.
290. *Carpatolechia alburnella* (Zeller, 1839) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI-VII.

291. *Carpatolechia fugitivella* (Zeller, 1839) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI-VII.
292. *Carpatolechia notatella* (Hübner, [1813]) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Davydovka. FP: VI.
293. *Carpatolechia proximella* (Hübner, 1796) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Petropavlovka, Davydovka. FP: V-VI.
294. *Teleiopsis diffinis* (Haworth, 1828) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Krasnyi Oktyabr`. FP: IX.
295. *Pseudotelphusa paripunctella* (Thunberg, 1794) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Petropavlovka, Davydovka. FP: V-VI.

Anacampsinae

296. *Syncopacma cinctella* (Clerck, 1759) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Samsonovo, Gulyai Pole, Davydovka. FP: VI-VII.
297. *Aproaerema anthyllidella* (Hübner, [1813]) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Gulyai Pole. FP: VI.
298. *Anacampsis blattariella* (Hübner, 1796) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Aksenovka, Politotdel, Davydovka, Atmos. FP: VII-X.
299. *Anacampsis populella* (Clerck, 1759) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Berezka. FP: VI-VII.
300. *Brachmia blandella* (Fabricius, 1798) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Gulyai Pole. FP: VII.
301. *Brachmia dimidiella* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Davydovka, Omsk, Atmos. FP: VI-VIII.

Dichomeridinae

302. *Helcystogramma albinervis* (Gerasimov, 1929) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Gulyai Pole. FP: VI.
303. *Helcystogramma arulensis* (Rebel, 1929) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Atrachi, Davydovka. FP: IV-VIII.
304. *Helcystogramma lineolella* (Zeller, 1839) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Krasnyi Oktyabr`. FP: V.
305. *Helcystogramma lutatella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI-VII.
306. *Helcystogramma rufescens* (Haworth, 1828) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Samsonovo, Sedelnikovo, Gulyai Pole. FP: VI-VII.
307. *Acompsia cinerella* (Clerck, 1759) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Samsonovo. FP: VI-VIII.
308. *Dichomeris derasella* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Davydovka, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr`. FP: VI.

309. *Dichomeris polypunctata* Park, 1994 – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Samsonovo, Atrachi. FP: VII-VIII.
310. *Acanthophila alacella* (Zeller, 1839) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Bolshiye Uki. FP: VI.
311. *Neofaculta infernella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Davydovka. FP: VI.
312. *Neofaculta taigana* Ponomarenko, 1998 – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Basly. FP: V.
313. *Nothris lemniscella* (Zeller, 1839) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Davydovka, Ebeity, Ul'zhai, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Buzan. FP: VIII-IX.
314. *Hypatima rhomboidella* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Atrachi. FP: VIII.
315. *Anarsia stepposella* Ponomarenko, 2002 – REF: Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020. LOC: Omsk. FP: VII.

Pterophoridae

Agdistinae

316. *Agdistis adactyla* (Hübner, 1823) – REF: Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Yakovlevka, Maiskyi, Davydovka, Omsk, Ebeity, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos, Buzan. FP: VII-VIII.
317. *Agdistis intermedia* Caradja, 1920 – REF: Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Nalimovo, Kordon, Urusovo, Ebeity, Leninsk, Ataichye, Ul'zhai, Sholack-sor, Atmos, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII. Fig. 15.
318. *Agdistis kulunda* Ustjuzhanin, 1991 – REF: Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Amrinskaya Balka, Krasnyi Oktyabr'. FP: VIII.

Platyptilinae

319. *Gillmeria macrornis* (Meyrick, 1930) – REF: Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Ebeity, Krasnyi Oktyabr'. FP: VIII.
320. *Gillmeria pallidactyla* (Haworth, 1811) – REF: Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Abakshikha, Yakovlevka, Samsonovo, Sedelnikovo, Keizes, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Lyubino, Davydovka, Krasnyi Oktyabr'. FP: VI-VIII.
321. *Gillmeria stenoptiloides* (Filipjev, 1927) – REF: Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Omsk, Atmos. FP: VII.
322. *Platyptilia calodactyla* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Ustjuzhanin 1998; Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Yakovlevka, Atrachi, Boyevoye, Spasskoye, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos. FP: VII-VIII.
323. *Platyptilia farfarellus* Zeller, 1867 – REF: Knyazev et al. 2019. LOC: Gulyai Pole. FP: VIII.

Figure 15. *Agdistis intermedia*, Ataichye, 23.VI.2014, photo by S.A. Knyazev.

324. *Platyptilia gonodactyla* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Ustjuzhanin 1998; Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Bolshiye Uki, Timshinyakovo, Petropavlovka, Borki, Davydovka, Omsk, Achair, Krasnyi Oktyabr`. FP: VI-VIII.
325. *Platyptilia nemoralis* Zeller, 1841 – REF: Knyazev et al. 2017. LOC: Yakovlevka, Krasnoyarka. FP: VI.
326. *Paraplatyptilia metzneri* (Zeller, 1841) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2019. LOC: Ebeity, Ul`zhai, Nikolaevka, Sholacksor. FP: VI-IX.
327. *Amblyptilia punctidactyla* (Haworth, 1811) – REF: Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Yakovlevka, Samsonovo, Timshinyakovo, Keizes, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Podgorodka, Davydovka. FP: V-IX.
328. *Stenoptilia annadactyla* Sutter, 1988 – REF: Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Atmos. FP: VIII.
329. *Stenoptilia bipunctidactyla* (Scopoli, 1763) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2019. LOC: Gulyai Pole. FP: VI-VIII.
330. *Stenoptilia eborinodactyla* Zagulajev, 1986 – REF: Knyazev et al. 2019. LOC: Atmos, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.
331. *Stenoptilia pneumonantes* (Büttner, 1880) – REF: Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Atrachi, Davydovka, Cherlack. FP: VI-VIII.

332. *Stenoptilia pterodactyla* (Linnaeus, 1761) – REF: Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Samsonovo, Timshinyakovo, Keizes, Petropavlovka, Amrinskaya Balka. FP: VI-VIII.
333. *Cnaemidophorus rhododactyla* ([Denis et Schuffermuller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2017; Knyazev et al. 2019. LOC: Keizes, Krutye Luki, Davydovka, Omsk. FP: VI-VII.
334. *Marasmarcha cinnamomea* (Staudinger, 1870) – REF: Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Maryanovka, Ataichye, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.
335. *Marasmarcha colossa* Caradja, 1920 – REF: Ustjuzhanin 1998; Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Solyanoye, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Novovarshavka, Buzan. FP: VI-VII.
336. *Marasmarcha rhypodactyla* (Staudinger, 1871) – REF: Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Krutye Luki, Sholacksor, Buzan. FP: VI-VII.
337. *Oxyptilus chrysodactyla* ([Denis et Schuffermuller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Samsonovo. FP: VIII.
338. *Oxyptilus ericetorum* (Stainton, 1851) – REF: Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Atmos. FP: VII.
339. *Oxyptilus parvidactylus* (Haworth, 1811) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2017. LOC: Atmos. FP: VII.
340. *Crombrugghia tristis* (Zeller, 1841) – REF: Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Petropavlovka, Davydovka, Ebeity, Cherlack, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos. FP: VI-VIII.
341. *Geina didactyla* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Ustjuzhanin 1998; Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Boyevoye. FP: VII-VIII.
342. *Capperia trichodactyla* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Petropavlovka, Boyevoye, Spasskoye, Atrachi, Davydovka, Krutye Luki, Amrinskaya Balka, Cherlack, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.
343. *Buckleria paludum* (Zeller, 1839) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2019. LOC: Ust-Ishim. FP: VII.

Pterophorinae

344. *Pterophorus pentadactyla* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Ustjuzhanin 1998; Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Berezka, Boyevoye, Maiskiy, Spasskoye, Podgorodka, Davydovka, Omsk, Cherlack, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos. FP: VI-VIII.
345. *Porritia galactodactyla* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2017. LOC: Yakovlevka. FP: VI.
346. *Tabulaephorus marptys* (Christoph, 1872) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2017. LOC: Nikolaevka, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.

347. *Merrifieldia leucodactyla* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Krasnyi Oktyabr`. FP: VI.
348. *Merrifieldia tridactyla* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Ustjuzhanin 1998; Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Achair, Nikolaevka, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Atmos. FP: VI-VII.
349. *Oidaematophorus lithodactyla* (Treitschke, 1833) – REF: Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Samsonovo, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole. FP: VII-VIII.
350. *Hellinsia carphodactyla* (Hübner, [1813]) – REF: Ustjuzhanin 1998; Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Petropavlovka, Isilkul`, Boyevoye, Davydovka, Omsk, Ebeity, Mikhailovka, Sholacksor, Nikolaevka, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.
351. *Hellinsia chrysocomae* (Ragonot, 1875) – REF: Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Ebeity, Omsk, Buzan. FP: VIII.
352. *Hellinsia didactylites* (Ström, 1785) – REF: Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Omsk. FP: VII.
353. *Hellinsia distincta* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855) – REF: Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Spasskoye, Buzan. FP: VII-VIII.
354. *Hellinsia inulae* (Zeller, 1852) – REF: Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Podgorodka, Davydovka, Amrinskaya Balka, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.
355. *Hellinsia lienigianus* (Zeller, 1852) – REF: Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Abakshikha, Bolshiye Uki, Sedelnikivo, Petropavlovka, Omsk. FP: VI-VIII.
356. *Hellinsia osteodactyla* (Zeller, 1841) – REF: Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Samsonovo, Ebeity, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Atmos. FP: VI-VII.
357. *Hellinsia tephradactyla* (Hübner, [1813]) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2019. LOC: Samsonovo. FP: VII.
358. *Hellinsia trimmatodactyla* (Christoph, 1872) – REF: Ustjuzhanin 1998; Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Boyevoye, Solyanoye, Krasnyi Oktyabr`. FP: VI-VIII.
359. *Emmelina monodactyla* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Ustjuzhanin 1998; Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Berezka, Spasskoye, Podgorodka, Davydovka, Omsk, Chelack, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Atmos, Buzan. FP: VII-IX.

Epermeniidae

360. *Epermenia illigerella* (Hübner, 1813) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Samsonovo, Davydovka. FP: VI-VII.
361. *Epermenia iniquella* (Wocke, 1867) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI-VII.
362. *Epermenia strictella* (Wocke, 1867) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Podgorodka. FP: X.

Choreutidae

363. *Prochoreutis shestediana* (Fabricius, 1776) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
364. *Choreutis diana* (Hübner, 1822) – REF: Sinev and Knyazev 2021. LOC: Atmas. FP: VII.

Galacticidae

365. *Galactica walsinghami* (Caradja, 1920) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2016. LOC: Ebeity, Ataichye, Ul'zhai, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.

Tortricidae

Tortricinae - Tortricini

366. *Acleris fimbriana* (Thunberg, 1791) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Timshinyakovo, Gulyai Pole. FP: IV-V, IX-X.
367. *Acleris hastiana* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Yakovlevka, Bolshiye Uki, Pospelovo, Timshinyakovo, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Podgorodka, Davydovka, Omsk, Tatarka. FP: IV-V, IX-X.
368. *Acleris lacordairana* (Duponchel, 1836) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Yakovlevka, Petropavlovka, Podgorodka. FP: IV-V, IX-X.
369. *Acleris laterana* (Fabricius, 1794) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Yakovlevka, Keizes, Petropavlovka, Serbryanoye, Podgorodka, Davydovka, Syropyatskoye. FP: IV-V, IX-X. Fig. 16.
370. *Acleris lipsiana* ([Denis et Sdchiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Bolshiye Uki, Samsonovo, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Novotroitskoye, Podgorodka, Davydovka, . FP: IV-V, IX-X.
371. *Acleris logiana* (Clerck, 1759) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Orekhovo, Ust-Ishim, Atak, Keizes, Okunevo, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Berezka, Aksenovka, Novotroitskoye. FP: IV-V, IX-XI. Fig. 17.
372. *Acleris lorquiniana* (Duponchel, 1835) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Abakshikha, Bolshiye Uki, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole. FP: IV-V, IX-X.
373. **Acleris maccana* (Treitschke, 1835) – LOC: Buzan. FP: IV-V, IX-X.
374. *Acleris notana* (Donovan, 1806) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ust-Ishim. FP: IV-V, IX-X.

Figure 16. *Acleris laterana*, Petropavlovka, 6.IX.2018, photo by S.A. Knyazev.

Figure 17. *Acleris logiana*, Petropavlovka, 4.X.2008, photo by S.A. Knyazev.

375. *Acleris permutana* (Duponchel, 1835) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Tatarka, Buzan. FP: IV-V, IX-X.
376. *Acleris ruscidana* (Hübner, [1799]) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Yakovlevka, Samsonovo, Gulyai Pole, Aksenovka, Davydovka, Tatarka. FP: IV-V, IX-X. Fig. 18.
377. *Acleris rufana* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Bolshiye Uki, Samsonovo, Timshinyakovo, Keizes, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Atrachi, Novotroitskoye, Davydovka, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Tatarka. FP: IV-V, IX-X.
378. *Acleris scabrana* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Davydovka, Atmos. FP: IV-V, IX-X.
379. *Acleris similis* Filipjev, 1931 – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ust-Ishim. FP: IV-V, IX-X.
380. *Acleris umbrana* (Hübner, [1799]) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Samsonovo, Petropavlovka, Podgorodka. FP: IV-V, IX-X.
381. *Croesia bergmanniana* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ermak. FP: VI.

Tortricinae - Cochylini

382. *Phtheochroa inopiana* (Haworth, 1811) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Gulyai Pole, Davydovka, Ul`zhai, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Ermak, Buzan. FP: VI-IX.
383. *Phtheochroa pistrinana* (Erschoff, 1877) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Petropavlovka, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Buzan. FP: VI.
384. *Phtheochroa retextana* (Erschoff, 1874) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki. FP: VI.
385. *Cochylimorpha alternana* (Stephens, 1834) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Basly, Samsonovo, Muromtsevo, Gulyai Pole, Urusovo, Atmos, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.
386. *Cochylimorpha armeniana* Joannis, 1891 – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ebeity, Amrinskaya Balka, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Mikhailovka. FP: VIII.
387. *Cochylimorpha asiana* (Kennel, 1899) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Davydovka, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Ul`zhai, Sholacksor, Ataichye. FP: VI.
388. *Cochylimorpha clathratana* (Staudinger, 1879) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Atmos. FP: V.
389. *Cochylimorpha cultana* (Lederer, 1855) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki. FP: VI.

390. *Cochylimorpha discopunctana* (Eversmann, 1844) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos, Alabota, Buzan. FP: VII-VIII.
391. *Cochylimorpha discolorana* (Kennel, 1899) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ataichye, Ul'zhai. FP: VI.
392. *Cochylimorpha fucatana* (Snellen, 1883) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Krasnyi Oktyabr', Ul'zhai, Nikolaevka, Sholacksor. FP: VI.
393. *Cochylimorpha obliquana* (Eversmann, 1844) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Buzan. FP: VII.
394. *Cochylimorpha perturbana* (Kennel, 1900) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Krasnyi Oktyabr'. FP: VIII.
395. *Cochylimorpha pyramidana* (Staudinger, 1870) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Krasnyi Oktyabr', Mikhailovka, Sholacksor, Bogdanovka, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.
396. *Cochylimorpha subwolniana* (Danilevsky, 1962) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Podgorodka, Davydovka, Bogdanovka, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Ataichye. FP: V-VI.
397. *Cochylimorpha wolniana* (Schleich, 1868) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
398. *Gynnidomorpha affinitana* (Douglas, 1846) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Krasnyi Oktyabr'. FP: VII.
399. *Gynnidomorpha albipalpana* (Zeller, 1847) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ataichye. FP: VI-VII.
400. *Gynnidomorpha contractana* (Zeller, 1847) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Atmos, Buzan. FP: VIII-IX.
401. *Gynnidomorpha manniana* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1839) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr'. FP: VI-VII.
402. *Gynnidomorpha minimana* (Caradja, 1916) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Samsonovo, Keizes, Gulyai Pole, Atmos. FP: VI-VIII.
403. *Gynnidomorpha permixtana* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Samsonovo, Gulyai Pole. FP: VII-VIII.
404. *Gynnidomorpha vectisana* (Humphreys et Westwood, 1845) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ust-Ishim. FP: VI.
405. *Agapeta hamana* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Vnukovsky, 1930; Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Knyazevo, Isilkul', Davydovka, Omsk, Amrinskaya Balka, Krasnyi Oktyabr'. FP: VI-VIII.
406. *Agapeta zoegana* (Linnaeus, 1767) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Omsk, Atmos, Buzan. FP: VII-VIII.
407. *Eugnosta lathoniana* (Hübner, [1800]) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Knyazevo, Boyevoye, Ermak, Buzan. FP: VII-VIII.
408. *Eupoecilia ambiguella* (Hübner, 1796) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Elnichnoye. FP: VII.

409. *Eupoecilia angustana* (Hübner, [1799]) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Keizes, Petropavlovka, Danilovo, Boyevoye, Urusovo, Davydovka, Omsk. FP: VI-VII.
410. *Eupoecilia cebrana* (Hübner, [1813]) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Samsonovo, Gulyai Pole, Davydovka, Omsk, Solyanoye, Nikolaevka, Buzan. FP: VI-VII.
411. *Eupoecilia citrinana* Razowski, 1960 – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Boyevoye, Omsk, Novovarshavka. FP: VI-VII.
412. *Eupoecilia sanguisorbana* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1856) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Davydovka, Novovarshavka. FP: VII-VIII.
413. *Aethes alatafica* (Danilevsky, 1962) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Omsk, Mikhailovka. FP: VII-VIII.
414. *Aethes cnicana* (Westwood, 1854) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Boyevoye. FP: VI.
415. *Aethes fennicana* M.Hering, 1924 – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Gulyai Pole. FP: VI-VII.
416. ***Aethes flagellana* (Duponchel, 1836) – LOC: Ul'zhai. FP: VII.
417. *Aethes francillana* (Fabricius, 1794) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Omsk, Ul'zhai. FP: VI-VII.
418. *Aethes hartmanniana* (Clerck, 1759) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Gulyai Pole. FP: VI.
419. *Aethes margaritana* (Haworth, 1811) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Omsk. FP: VII.
420. *Aethes moribundana* Staudinger, 1859 – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Samsonovo, Atrachi, Novotroitskoye, Davydovka, Bogdanovka, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos, Buzan. FP: V-VIII.
421. *Aethes rubigana* (Treitschke, 1830) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Samsonovo, Knyazevo, Davydovka, Krasnyi Oktyabr'. FP: VII-VIII.
422. *Aethes smeathmanniana* (Fabricius, 1781) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
423. *Aethes tessera* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Atmos. FP: VI.
424. *Aethes triangulana* (Treitschke, 1835) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Urusovo, Novotroitskoye, Davydovka, Atmos. FP: V-VI.
425. *Aethes williana* (Brahm, 1791) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Omsk. FP: VI-VII.
426. *Cochylidia heydeniana* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Omsk, Ul'zhai, Krasnyi Oktyabr'. FP: V-VI.

Figure 18. *Acleris roscidana*, Yakovlevka, 20.V.2018, photo by S.A. Knyazev.

Figure 19. *Falseuncaria degreyana*, Buzan, 1.VI.2018, photo by S.A. Knyazev.

427. *Cochylidia implicitana* (Wocke, 1856) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Keizes, Atrachi, Podgorodka, Davydovka, Ebeity, Ul'zhai, Ataichye, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.
428. *Cochylidia richteriana* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1837) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Omsk. FP: VII.
429. *Cochylidia subroseana* (Haworth, 1911) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Davydovka. FP: VI.
430. *Cochylis dubitana* (Hübner, [1799]) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Samsonovo, Timshinyakovo, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Podgorodka, Davydovka, Omsk, Buzan. FP: V-VIII.
431. *Cochylis nana* (Haworth, 1811) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Samsonovo, Omsk. FP: V-VI.
432. *Cochylis posterana* Zeller, 1847 – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Samsonovo, Boyevoye, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos. FP: V-IX.
433. *Falseuncaria degreyana* (McLachlan, 1869) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Petropavlovka, Atrachi, Davydovka, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Ul'zhai, Ataichye, Buzan. FP: V-VIII. Fig. 19.

Tortricinae - Euliini

434. *Eulia ministrana* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Boyevoye, Podgorodka, Davydovka, Krasnyi Oktyabr'. FP: VI.

Tortricinae - Cnephasiini

435. *Xerocnephasia rigana* (Sodoffsky, 1829) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Krasnyi Oktyabr', Buzan. FP: V-VII.
436. *Doloploca punctulana* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Podgorodka. FP: V.
437. **Doloploca praeviella* (Erschoff, 1877) – LOC: Buzan. FP: IV.
438. *Eana argentana* (Clerck, 1759) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Davydovka. FP: VI.
439. *Eana incanana* (Stephens, 1852) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Samsonovo, Atmos. FP: VI-VIII.
440. *Eana osseana* (Scopoli, 1763) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki. FP: VII-VIII.
441. *Cnephasia alticolana* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Sedelnikovo, Danilovo, Nikolaevka, Krasnyi Oktyabr'. FP: VI-VII. Fig. 20.
442. *Cnephasia stephensiana* (Doubleday, 1849) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki. FP: VI-VII.

Tortricinae - Archipini

443. *Archips betulana* (Hübner, 1787) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Atrachi, Berezka, Davydovka, Kabanye, Nikolaevka, Atmos, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.
444. *Argyrotaenia ljungiana* (Thunberg, 1797) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Petropavlovka, Podgorodka, Krasnyi Oktyabr`. FP: V.
445. *Choristoneura diversana* (Hübner, [1817]) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Atrachi, Omsk, Cherlack, Atmos. FP: VI-VIII.
446. *Ptycholomoides aeriferanus* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Samsonovo. FP: VII-VIII.
447. *Ptycholoma lecheana* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Gulyai Pole, Boyevoye, Davydovka, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr`. FP: VI.
448. *Pandemis chondrillana* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1860) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Omsk. FP: VII.
449. *Pandemis heparana* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Samsonovo, Keizes, Koshkul`, Davydovka, Omsk, Atmos. FP: VI-VIII.
450. *Pandemis cerasana* (Hübner, 1786) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Atrachi, Urusovo, Davydovka, Omsk, Atmos. FP: VI-VIII.
451. *Syndemis musculana* (Hübner, [1799]) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Bolshiye Uki, Atak, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Serebryanoye, Novotroitskoye, Podgorodka, Davydovka, Omsk, Solyanoye, Krasnyi Oktyabr`. FP: V-VIII.
452. *Lozotaenia forsterana* (Fabricius, 1781) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Basly, Samsonovo, Keizes, Gulyai Pole. FP: VII-VIII.
453. *Aphelia unitana* (Hübner, [1799]) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Orekhovo, Gulyai Pole, Davydovka, Omsk, Atmos. FP: VII-VIII.
454. *Aphelia viburnana* (Fabricius, 1787) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Proletarskiy, Davydovka. FP: VI-VII.
455. *Clepsis neglectana* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Podgorodka, Omsk. FP: VI-VII.
456. *Clepsis pallidana* (Fabricius, 1776) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Atrachi, Serebryanoye, Verkhneilyinka, Solyanoye, Ul'zhai, Atmos, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.
457. *Clepsis rurinana* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Samsonovo, Petropavlovka, Podgorodka. FP: VI-VII.

458. *Clepsis senecionana* (Hübner, [1819]) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Bolshiye Uki, Samsonovo, Atak, Gulyai Pole, Davydovka, Bogdanovka. FP: V-VI.
459. *Clepsis spectrana* (Treitschke, 1830) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Gulyai Pole, Knyazevo, Atmos. FP: VI-VII.
460. *Adoxophyes orana* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1834) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Atrachi, Davydovka, Omsk, Amrinskaya Balka. FP: VI-VIII.

Tortricinae - Ramapesiini

461. *Periclepsis cinctana* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Buzan. FP: VI.
462. *Philedone gerningana* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Gulyai Pole, Nalimovo. FP: VI-VIII.
463. *Capua vulgana* (Frölich, 1828) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Petropavlovka, Boyevoye, Davydovka, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr`. FP: VI.

Olethreutinae - Endotheniini

464. *Endothenia quadrimaculana* (Haworth, 1811) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Listvyagi, Bolshiye Uki, Petropavlovka, Urusovo, Berezka, Davydovka, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Atmos, Novovarshavka. FP: VI-VIII.
465. *Endothenia marginana* (Haworth, 1811) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Gulyai Pole, Atrachi, Koshkul`, Davydovka, Omsk, Bogdanovka, Ataichye, Mikhailovka, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Atmos, Buzan. FP: V-VIII.
466. *Endothenia nigricostana* (Haworth, 1811) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.

Olethreutinae - Bactrini

467. *Bactra furfurana* (Haworth, 1811) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Bolshiye Uki, Moskalenki, Syropyat-skoye, Davydovka, Atmos, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.
468. *Bactra lancealana* (Hübner, 1799) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Listvyagi, Davydovka, Ataichye, Mikhailovka, Atmos. FP: VI-VIII.

469. *Bactra robustana* (Christoph, 1872) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Gulyai Pole, Davydovka, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.

Olethreutinae - Olethreutini

470. *Aterpia circumfluxana* (Christoph, 1881) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Gulyai Pole. FP: VII.
471. *Aterpia chalybeia* Falkovitsh, 1966 – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Gulyai Pole. FP: VI.
472. *Apotomis betuletana* (Haworth, 1811) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Gulyai Pole, Atrachi, Boyevoye, Davydovka, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Atmos, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.
473. *Apotomis capreana* (Hübner, [1817]) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Petropavlovka, Danilovo, Davydovka. FP: VI-VII.
474. *Apotomis infida* (Heinrich, 1926) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Elnichnoye, Omsk, Atmos. FP: VI.
475. *Apotomis inundana* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Keizes, Nizhnyaya Omka. FP: VII.
476. *Apotomis sororculana* (Zetterstedt, [1839]) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Samsonovo, Petropavlovka, Davydovka, Omsk. FP: V-VII.
477. *Apotomis turbidana* (Hübner, [1825]) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Petropavlovka, Isilkul`, Davydovka. FP: VI-VII.
478. *Orthotaenia undulana* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Orekhovo, Elnichnoye, Gulyai Pole, 2624 km, Davydovka, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Nikolaevka, Atmos. FP: VI-VII.
479. *Pseudohermenias abietana* (Fabricius, 1787) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Podgorodka, Omsk. FP: VI-VIII.
480. *Hedya dimidiana* (Clerck, 1759) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Samsonovo, Timshinyakovo, Sedelnikovo. FP: VII.
481. *Hedya ochroleucana* (Frölich, 1828) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Russkaya Polyana, Buzan. FP: VII.
482. *Hedya salicella* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Davydovka, Omsk, Atmos. FP: VI-IX.
483. *Metendothenia atropunctana* (Zetterstedt, [1839]) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Petropavlovka, Davydovka, Solyanoye, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Buzan. FP: V-VII.
484. *Cymolomia hartigiana* (Saxesen, 1840) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Samsonovo, Omsk. FP: VI-VII.

485. *Argyroploce lediana* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Koshkul'. FP: VI-VII.
486. *Olethreutes arcuellus* (Clerck, 1759) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Boyevoye, Davydovka, Omsk, Ataichye, Nikolaevka, Atmos. FP: VI-VII.
487. *Olethreutes subtilanus* (Falkovitsh, 1959) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Elnichnoye. FP: VII.
488. *Phiaris bipunctana* (Fabricius, 1794) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Sedelnikovo, Elnichnoye, Gulyai Pole, Koshkul'. FP: VI-VII.
489. *Phiaris metallicana* (Hübner, [1799]) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Elnichnoye, Petropavlovka, Omsk. FP: VI-VII.
490. *Phiaris micana* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Gulyai Pole. FP: VI-VII.
491. *Phiaris nordeggana* (McDunnough, 1922) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Gulyai Pole. FP: VI.
492. *Phiaris obsoletana* (Zetterstedt, [1839]) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Samsonovo. FP: VI.
493. **Celypha anatoliana* (Caradja, 1916) – LOC: Tatarka. FP: IX.
494. *Celypha cespitana* (Hübner, [1817]) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Urusovo, Davydovka, Omsk, Ebeity, Amrinskaya Balka, Atmos, Krasnyi Oktyabr'. FP: VI-VIII.
495. *Celypha confictana* (Kennel, 1901) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Gulyai Pole, Berezka, Ataichye, Ul'zhai, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.
496. *Celypha flavipalpata* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Omsk, Atmos, Krasnyi Oktyabr'. FP: VI-VIII.
497. *Celypha rufana* (Scopoli, 1763) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Listvyagi, Bolshiye Uki, Samsonovo, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Sholacksor. FP: VI-VIII.
498. *Celypha rurestrana* (Duponchel, 1843) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Atmos. FP: VII.
499. *Celypha striana* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Keizes, Urusovo, Boyevoye, 2624 km, Davydovka, Omsk, Verkhneilyinka, Atmos, Tatarka. FP: VI-VIII.
500. *Syricoris lacunana* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Abakshikha, Yakovlevka, Bolshiye Uki, Sedelnikovo, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Podgorodka, Davydovka, Omsk. FP: VI-VIII.
501. *Syricoris rivulana* (Scopoli, 1763) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Samsonovo, Gulyai Pole, Nalimovo, Isilkul', Proletarskiy, Politotdel, Davydovka, Omsk, Atmos. FP: VI-VIII.

502. *Syricoris tiedemanniana* (Zeller, 1845) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Yakovlevka, Bolshiye Uki, Samsonovo, Gulyai Pole. FP: VI-VII.
503. *Piniphila bifasciana* (Haworth, 1811) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Elnichnoye. FP: VII.
504. *Pseudosciaphila branderiana* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Abakshikha, Yakovlevka, Samsonovo, Koshkul', Boyevoe, Davydovka. FP: VI-VII.
505. *Eudemis porphyrana* (Hübner, [1799]) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Gulyai Pole. FP: VII.

Olethreutinae - Lobesiini

506. *Lobesia abscissana* (Doubleday, 1849) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Podgorodka, Davydovka. FP: VI.
507. *Lobesia bicinctana* (Duponchel, 1844) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Atrachi, Omsk. FP: VIII.
508. *Lobesia indusiana* (Zeller, 1847) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ataichye, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.

Olethreutinae - Enarmoniini

509. *Ancylis (Anchylopera) apicella* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Samsonovo, Atak. FP: V.
510. *Ancylis (Anchylopera) badiana* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Samsonovo, Sedelnikovo, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Davydovka. FP: V-VII.
511. *Ancylis (Anchylopera) myrtiliana* (Treitschke, 1830) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Petropavlovka. FP: VI.
512. *Ancylis (Anchylopera) selenana* (Guenée, 1845) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Samsonovo. FP: VI.
513. *Ancylis (Anchylopera) tineana* (Hübner, [1799]) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ust-Ishim. FP: VI.
514. *Ancylis (Ancyliis) diminutana* (Haworth, 1811) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bogdanovka. FP: V.
515. *Ancylis (Ancyliis) geminana* (Donovan, 1806) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Samsonovo, Atak, Petropavlovka, Davydovka, Solyanoye, Buzan. FP: V-VI.
516. *Ancylis (Ancyliis) kenneli* Kuznetzov, 1962 – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Davydovka, Omsk, Solyanoye, Bogdanovka. FP: V-VI.
517. *Ancylis (Ancyliis) laetana* (Fabricius, 1775) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Samsonovo, Koshkul', Davydovka. FP: VI-VII.

Figure 20. *Cnephasia alticolana*, Krasnyi Oktyabr', ex larva, 3.XI.2020, S.M. Saikina leg., photo by S.A. Knyazev.

Figure 21. *Ancylis unguicella*, Gulyai Pole, 16.VI.2018, photo by S.A. Knyazev.

518. *Ancylis (Ancylis) obtusana* (Haworth, 1811) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Petropavlovka. FP: V-VI.
519. *Ancylis (Ancylis) unguicella* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Basly, Gulyai Pole. FP: V-VI. Fig. 21.
520. *Ancylis (Ancylis) uncella* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Samsonovo, Krasnyi Yar, Podgorodka, Davydovka, Krasnyi Oktyabr'. FP: V-VI.
521. *Ancylis (Ancylis) upupana* (Treitschke, 1835) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Timshinyakovo, Petropavlovka, Danilovo. FP: VI.

Olethreutinae - Eucosmini

522. *Gypsonoma minutana* (Hübner, [1799]) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
523. *Gypsonoma nitidulana* (Lienig & Zeller, 1846) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Samsonovo, Davydovka, Atmos. FP: V-VI.
524. *Gypsonoma sociana* (Haworth, 1811) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
525. *Gibberifera simplana* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1836) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Boyevoye, Omsk. FP: VI.
526. *Epinotia (Epinotia) nanana* (Treitschke, 1835) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
527. *Epinotia (Epinotia) ramella* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Samsonovo, Atrachi, Podgorodka, Davydovka, Omsk, Atmos. FP: VII-VIII.
528. *Epinotia (Evetria) bilunana* (Haworth, 1811) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Boyevoye, Davydovka, Omsk, Solyanoye. FP: VI.
529. *Epinotia (Evetria) cinereana* (Haworth, 1811) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Boyevoye, Omsk, Syropyat-skoye. FP: VIII-IX.
530. *Epinotia (Evetria) crenana* (Hübner, [1799]) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Yakovlevka. FP: V.
531. *Epinotia (Evetria) demarniana* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1840) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Sedelnikovo, Urusovo, Boyevoye, Davydovka, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Nikolaevka, Buzan. FP: VI-VII.
532. *Epinotia (Evetria) nisella* (Clerck, 1759) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Samsonovo, Keizes, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Atrachi, Aksenovka, Davydovka, Omsk, Atmos. FP: VIII-X.

533. *Epinotia (Evetria) solandriana* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Yakovlevka, Samsonovo, Petropavlovka, Atrachi, Omsk, Syropyatskoye, Buzan. FP: VIII-IX.
534. *Epinotia (Evetria) tetraquetrana* (Haworth, 1811) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Atak. Keizes, Petropavlovka, Krasnyi Yar, Davydovka, Solyanoye, Bogdanovka, Buzan. FP: V-VI.
535. *Epinotia (Evetria) thapsiana* (Zeller, 1847) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Urusovo, Koshkul', Omsk, Nikolaevka. FP: VI-VII.
536. *Epinotia (Evetria) trigonella* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Gulyai Pole, Atrachi. FP: VIII.
537. *Zeiraphera griseana* (Hübner, [1799]) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI-VIII.
538. *Zeiraphera rufimitrana* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Boyevoye. FP: VI-VIII.
539. *Spilonota laricana* (Heinemann, 1863) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI-VII.
540. *Spilonota ocellana* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Boyevoye, Omsk, Cherklack. FP: V-VII.
541. *Rhopobota naevana* (Hübner, [1817]) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Samsonovo. FP: VIII.
542. *Rhopobota stagnana* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Gulyai Pole. FP: V.
543. *Retinia perangustana* (Snellen, 1883) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Podgorodka, Omsk. FP: V-VI.
544. *Retinia resinella* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Podgorodka. FP: VI.
545. *Rhyacionia duplana* (Hübner, [1813]) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Yakovlevka, Gulyai Pole. FP: IV.
546. *Rhyacionia pinicolana* (Doubleday, 1849) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Omsk, Atmos. FP: VI-VII.
547. *Rhyacionia pinivorana* (Zeller, 1846) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Atak. Podgorodka, Omsk. FP: V-VI.
548. *Blastesthia posticana* (Zetterstedt, 1839) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
549. *Blastesthia turionella* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Petropavlovka. FP: VI.
550. *Eriopsela quadrana* (Hübner, [1813]) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Novotroitskoye, Davydovka, Krasnyi Oktyabr'. FP: V.
551. *Thiodia citrana* (Hübner, [1799]) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Omsk, Sholacksor, Atmos. FP: VI.

552. *Thiodia torridana* (Lederer, 1859) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Boyevoe, Davydovka, Omsk, Ataichye. FP: VII.
553. *Lepteucosma huebneriana* Kocak, 1980 – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Samsonovo, Davydovka, Ataichye, Buzan. FP: VI-X.
554. *Notocelia cynosbatella* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Vnukovsky 1930; Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Sedelnikovo, Elnichnoye, Davydovka, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr'. FP: VI-VII.
555. *Notocelia incarnatana* (Hübner, 1800) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Samsonovo, Omsk, Amrinskaya Balka, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos, Buzan. FP: VII-VIII.
556. *Notocelia roborana* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI-VII.
557. *Epiblema cirsiana* (Zeller, 1843) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole. FP: VI.
558. *Epiblema foenella* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Samsonovo, Urusovo, Boyevoe, Podgorodka, Omsk, Atmos. FP: VI-VIII.
559. *Epiblema fuchsiana* (Röslerstamm, 1877) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Serebryanoye, Podgorodka, Davydovka, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Nikolaevka, Ul'zhai, Atmos, Buzan. FP: V-VIII.
560. *Epiblema grandaevana* (Lienig et Zeller, 1846) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Gulyai Pole. FP: VI.
561. *Epiblema graphana* (Freyer, 1835) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Danilovo, Gulyai Pole, Urusovo, Omsk, Atmos. FP: VI-VIII.
562. *Epiblema hepaticana* (Treitschke, 1835) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Samsonovo, Timshinyakovo. FP: VI.
563. *Epiblema junctana* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1856) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Orekhovo, Bolshiye Uki, Davydovka, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Sholacksor, Buzan. FP: VI.
564. *Epiblema similana* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Petropavlovka, Podgorodka. FP: VI.
565. *Eucosma aemulana* (Schläger, 1849) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Davydovka. FP: VI.
566. *Eucosma apocrypha* Falkovitsh, 1964 – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Omsk, Ataichye, Ul'zhai, Atmos. FP: VI-VIII.
567. *Eucosma aspidiscana* (Hübner, [1817]) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Davydovka. FP: VI.
568. *Eucosma balatonana* (Osthelder, 1937) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Yakovlevka. FP: VII.
569. **Eucosma caliacrana* Caradja, 1931 – LOC: Timshinyakovo. FP: V.
570. *Eucosma campoliliana* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Sedelnikovo. FP: VI.

571. *Eucosma cana* (Haworth, 1811) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Sedelnikovo, Atrachi, Knyazevo, Podgorodka, Davydovka, Atmos. FP: VI-VIII.
572. *Eucosma clarescens* Kuznetsov, 1964 – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
573. *Eucosma conterminana* (Guenée, 1845) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Omsk, Amrinskaya Balka, Mikhailovka, Atmos. FP: VI-VIII.
574. **Eucosma fervidana* (Zeller, 1847) – LOC: Buzan. FP: VIII.
575. *Eucosma flavispecula* Kuznetsov, 1964 – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Omsk, Novovarshavka, Buzan. FP: VII-VIII.
576. *Eucosma fulvana* (Stephens, 1835) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Krasnyi Oktyabr`. FP: VI.
577. *Eucosma hohenwartiana* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Samsonovo, Sedelnikovo, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Davydovka, Ataichye, Atmos. FP: VI-VII.
578. *Eucosma krygeri* (Rebel, 1937) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Leninsk, Ataichye, Sholacksor, Buzan. FP: VI.
579. *Eucosma lacteana* (Treitschke, 1835) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Omsk, Sholacksor, Buzan. FP: VII.
580. *Eucosma metzneriana* (Treitschke, 1830) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Sedelnikovo, Gulyai Pole, Davydovka, Solyanoye, Krasnyi Oktyabr`. FP: VI-VII.
581. *Eucosma multifasciana* Budashkin et Dubatolov, 2009 – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Davydovka, Omsk, Ataichye, Ul`zhai. FP: VI-VII.
582. *Eucosma obumbratana* (Lienig & Zeller, 1846) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Buzan. FP: VII.
583. *Eucosma paetulana* (Kennel, 1901) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Davydovka, Ebeity, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Mikhailovka, Ul`zhai. FP: VI-VIII.
584. *Eucosma pergratana* (Rebel, 1914) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ebeity. FP: VIII.
585. *Eucosma pupillana* (Clerck, 1759) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Atmos. FP: VIII.
586. *Eucosma tundrana* (Kennel, 1900) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Davydovka, Omsk. FP: VI-VII.
587. *Eucosma wimmerana* (Treitschke, 1835) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Sedelnikovo, Okunevo, Gulyai Pole, Knyazevo, Davydovka, Leninsk, Sholacksor, Bogdanovka. FP: V-VII.
588. *Epibactra immundana* (Eversmann, 1844) = sareptana (Herrich-Schäffer, 1861) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ebeity, Ul`zhai. FP: VIII-IX.
589. *Pelochrista (Pelochrista) apheliana* (Kennel, 1901) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Atrachi, Davydovka, Atmos, Buzan. FP: VII-VIII.

590. *Pelochrista (Pelochrista) decolorana* (Freyer, 1842) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Boyevoye. FP: VII.
591. *Pelochrista (Pelochrista) infidana* (Hübner, [1824]) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ebeity, Atmos, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Ermak, Buzan. FP: VIII.
592. *Pelochrista (Pelochrista) mollitana* (Zeller, 1847) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Samsonovo, Gulyai Pole. FP: VII-VIII.
593. *Pelochrista (Pseudeucosma) arabescana* (Eversmann, 1844) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Boyevoye, Davydovka, Omsk, Ul`zhai, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Atmos, Buzan. FP: VII-IX.
594. *Pelochrista (Pseudeucosma) huebneriana* (Zeller, 1846) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Davydovka, Ebeity, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Ataichye, Mikhailovka, Atmos, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.
595. *Pelochrista (Pseudeucosma) umbraculana* (Eversmann, 1844) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Ebeity. FP: VII-VIII.

Olethreutinae - Grapholitini

596. *Dichrorampha acuminatana* (Lienig et Zeller, 1846) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI-VII.
597. *Dichrorampha insperata* (Danilevsky, 1960) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Samsonovo, Gulyai Pole, Atrachi. FP: VIII.
598. *Dichrorampha petiverella* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Podgorodka, Krasnyi Oktyabr`. FP: VI-VIII.
599. **Dichrorampha sedatana* Busck, 1906 – LOC: Timshinyakovo. FP: V.
600. *Dichrorampha sequana* (Hübner, [1799]) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Gulyai Pole. FP: VI.
601. *Dichrorampha simpliciana* (Haworth, 1811) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Samsonovo, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Atrachi, Politotdel, Davydovka, Podgorodka, Omsk. FP: VI-VIII.
602. *Dichrorampha uralensis* (Danilevsky, 1948) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Davydovka, Atmos. FP: VI.
603. *Grapholita andabatana* (Wolff, 1957) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Petropavlovka. FP: VII.
604. *Grapholita caecana* Schläger, 1847 – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
605. *Grapholita funebrana* (Treitschke, 1835) – REF: Shvetsova 1959; Danilevsky, Kuznetsov 1968; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI-VIII.
606. *Grapholita gemmiferana* (Treitschke, 1835) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Podgorodka, Davydovka, Buzan. FP: V-VI.
607. *Grapholita inopinata* (Heinrich, 1928) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI-VII.

608. *Grapholita jungiella* (Linnaeus, 1761) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Davydovka. FP: V.
609. *Grapholita nigrostriana* Snellen, 1883 – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Ataichye. FP: VI.
610. *Grapholita orobana* Treitschke, 1830 – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Davydovka, Omsk. FP: VII.
611. **Pammene aurana* (Fabricius, 1775) – LOC: Lyubino. FP: VI.
612. **Pammene insulana* (Guenée, 1845) – LOC: Verkhneilyinka. FP: V.
613. *Pammene obscurana* (Stephens, 1834) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Omsk, Nikolaevka, Buzan. FP: VI.
614. *Cydia cornucopiae* (Tengström, 1869) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Podgorodka. FP: VIII.
615. *Cydia exquisitana* (Rebel, 1889) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Omsk. FP: VII.
616. *Cydia illutana* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Atmos. FP: VIII.
617. *Cydia intexta* (Kuznetsov, 1962) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Atmos. FP: VIII.
618. *Cydia nigricana* (Fabricius, 1794) – REF: Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Koshkul'. FP: VII.
619. *Cydia oxytropidis* (Martini, 1912) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Atmos. FP: VII.
620. *Cydia pomonella* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Kulik, Shvetsova 1940; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Boyevoye, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr'. FP: VI-VII.
621. *Cydia succedana* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019. LOC: Atmos. FP: VII.

Pyralidae

Galleriinae

622. *Aphomia sociella* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Omsk, Atmos. FP: VI.
623. *Aphomia zelleri* Joannis, 1932 – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Ul'zhai, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos, Buzan. FP: VII-IX.
624. *Lamoria anella* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Solyanoye, Ermak, Russkaya Polyana. FP: VI.
625. *Galleria mellonella* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Omsk. FP: VIII.

Pyralinae

626. *Hypotia massilialis* (Duponchel, 1832) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Atmos, Buzan. FP: VI-VII.
627. *Synaphe bombycalis* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Amrinskaya Balka, Leninsk, Sholacksor, Ermak, Alabota. FP: VI-VII.
628. *Hypsopygia costalis* (Fabricius, 1775) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Davydovka, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Atmos, Buzan. FP: VI-X.
629. *Hypsopygia glaucinalis* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Knyazevo, Berezka, Omsk. FP: VI-VII.
630. *Pyralis farinalis* Linnaeus, 1758 – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Knyazevo, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Atmos. FP: V-VIII.
631. *Pyralis perversalis* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1849) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Ataichye, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Tatarka, Buzan. FP: VII-VIII.
632. *Pyralis regalis* [Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775 – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Samsonovo, Sedelnikovo, Petropavlovka, Berezka, Davydovka. FP: VII-VIII.
633. *Aglossa pinguinalis* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Omsk. FP: IV-VI.
634. *Aglossa dimidiata* (Haworth, 1829) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Davydovka, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Atmos. FP: IV-VII.

Phycitinae

635. *Salebriopsis albicilla* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1849) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Davydovka. FP: VI.
636. *Ortholepis betulae* (Goeze, 1778) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Atrachi, Berezka, Davydovka, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Atmos, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.
637. *Pyla fusca* (Haworth, 1811) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Podgorodka, Omsk, Syropyatskoye, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Mikhailovka, Buzan. FP: VI-IX.
638. *Pempeliella ornatella* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Ataichye, Atmos. FP: VI.
639. *Catastia marginea* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Omsk, Kulikovo, Presnovka, Orlovka, Buzan. FP: VI. Fig. 22.
640. *Polopeustis altensis* (Wocke, 1862) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Davydovka. FP: VII.
641. *Sciota adelphella* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1836) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Davydovka, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Atmos. FP: VI-VII.

642. *Sciota fumella* (Eversmann, 1844) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Bolshiye Uki, Sedelnikovo, Gulyai Pole, Urusovo, Davydovka. FP: VI-VII.
643. *Sciota hostilis* (Stephens, 1834) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Samsonovo, Danilovo. FP: VI-VII.
644. *Sciota lucipetella* (Jalava, 1978) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Davydovka. FP: V-VII.
645. *Sciota marmorata* (Alphéraky, 1878) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Knyazovo, Omsk, Atmos. FP: VI-VII.
646. *Sciota rhenella* (Zincken, 1818) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Knyazovo, Davydovka, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos. FP: V-VII.
647. *Selagia argyrella* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Politotdel, Davydovka, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr'. FP: VI-VII.
648. *Selagia spadicella* (Hübner, 1796) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Moskalenki, Ebeity, Atmos, Alabota, Buzan. FP: VII-VIII.
649. *Pima boisduvaliella* (Guenée, 1845) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Atai-chye, Atmos. FP: VI-VIII.
650. *Oncocera semirubella* (Scopoli, 1763) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Timshinyakovo, Gulyai Pole, Omsk, Verkhneilyinka, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos, Buzan. FP: VI-IX.
651. *Laodamia faecella* (Zeller, 1839) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Bolshiye Murly, Gulyai Pole, Davydovka, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Mikhailovka, Atmos, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.
652. *Pempelia alpigenella* (Duponchel, 1836) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Atmos, Buzan. FP: VII-VIII.
653. *Rhodophaea formosa* (Haworth, 1811) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Urusovo, Podgorodka, Davydovka. FP: VI.
654. *Dioryctria abietella* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Samsonovo, Atak, Petropavlovka, Kordon, Podgorodka, Omsk, Atmos. FP: V-VIII. Fig. 23.
655. *Hypochalcia ahenella* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Listvyagi, Bolshiye Uki, Sedelnikovo, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Koshkul', Urusovo, Krasnoyarka, Podgorodka. FP: VI-VIII.
656. *Hypochalcia propinquella* (Eversmann, 1842) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Knyazovo, Davydovka, Mikhailovka, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.
657. *Hypochalcia dignella* (Hübner, 1796) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2017. LOC: Nikolaevka. FP: VI.
658. *Epischnia ampliata* Heinemann, 1864 – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Ul'zhai. FP: VIII.
659. *Epischnia illotella* Zeller, 1839 – REF: Knyazev et al. 2017. LOC: Sholacksor. FP: VI.

660. *Furcata advenella* (Zincken, 1818) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Samsonovo, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.
661. *Lymphia chalybella* (Eversmann, 1844) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Davydovka. FP: V-VI.
662. *Apomyelois bistriatella* (Hulst, 1887) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Gulyai Pole, Atrachi. FP: VII-VIII.
663. *Glyptoteles leucacrinella* Zeller, 1848 – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Omsk. FP: VII.
664. *Episcythrastis tetricella* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Davydovka, Solyanoye, Poltavka. FP: V-VI.
665. *Myelois circumvolta* (Fourcroy, 1785) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Bolshiye Uki, Gulyai Pole, Koshkul', Davydovka, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Russkaya Polyana. FP: VI-VII.
666. *Cremonophila sedacovella* (Eversmann, 1851) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Krasnoyarka, Omsk, Atmos. FP: VI.
667. *Asalebria geminella* (Eversmann, 1844) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos. FP: VII.
668. *Isauria dilucidella* (Duponchel, 1836) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Knyazev, Omsk, Ebeity, Verkhneilyinka, Solyanoye, Ul'zhai, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos, Buzan. FP: IV-VIII.
669. *Eucarpia vinetella* (Fabricius, 1787) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Urusovo, Omsk, Ataichye, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos. FP: VI.
670. *Pogonotrophus allotriella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Ebeity, Buzan. FP: IV-V. Fig. 24.
671. *Gymnancyla canella* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2019. LOC: Ermak, Buzan. FP: VII-VIII.
672. *Zophodia grossulariella* (Hübner, [1809]) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Atak, Keizes, Muromtsevo, Podgorodka, Davydovka. FP: V-VI.
673. *Euzophera cinerosella* (Zeller, 1839) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Petropavlovka, Omsk, Verkhneilyinka, Solyanoye, Sholacksor, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos, Buzan. FP: V-VIII.
674. *Cymbalorissa fuliginosella* (Heinemann, 1865) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Samsonovo, Gulyai Pole, Omsk, Atmos. FP: VI-VIII.
675. *Nyctegretis lineana* (Scopoli, 1786) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Atrachi, Omsk, Verkhneilyinka, Solyanoye, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.
676. *Ancylosoma substratellum* (Christoph, 1877) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Krasnyi Oktyabr', Ul'zhai, Sholacksor, Ataichye, Buzan. FP: V-VIII.
677. *Ancylosis cinnamomella* (Duponchel, 1836) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Krasnyi Oktyabr', Buzan. FP: V-VIII.
678. *Ancylosis oblitella* (Zeller, 1848) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Knyazev, Boyevoye, Omsk, Ebeity, Verkhneilyinka, Solyanoye, Tatarka, Buzan. FP: V-IX.

Figure 22. *Catastia marginea*, Khlebodarovka, 5.VI.2021, photo by S.A. Knyazev.

Figure 23. *Dioryctria abietella*, Podgorodka, 10.VI.2014, photo by S.A. Knyazev.

Figure 24. *Pogonotrophus allotriella*, Buzan, 26.IV.2020, photo by S.A. Knyazev.

679. *Ancylosis roscidella* (Eversmann, 1844) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Krasnyi Oktyabr', Buzan. FP: V-VIII.
680. *Homoeosoma nebulella* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Atrachi, Moskalenki, Omsk, Bogdanovka, Ul'zhai, Atmos. FP: VI-VIII.
681. *Phycitodes albatella* (Ragonot, 1887) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Atmos. FP: VII.
682. *Phycitodes binaevella* (Hübner, [1813]) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Basly, Petropavlovka, Atrachi, Urusovo, Podgorodka, Davydovka, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos. FP: VI-IX.
683. *Phycitodes lacteella* (Rotschild, 1915) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Krasnyi Oktyabr'. FP: V.
684. *Phycitodes maritima* (Tengström, 1848) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Omsk, Ul'zhai. FP: VI-VIII.
685. *Phycitodes saxicola* (Vaughan, 1870) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Davydovka, Atmos. FP: VI-VII.
686. *Plodia interpunctella* (Hübner, [1813]) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Omsk. FP: I-IX.
687. *Anerastia lotella* (Hübner, [1813]) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos. FP: VI-VIII.

Crambidae

Crambinae

688. *Chilo phragmitella* (Hübner, [1805]) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos. FP: V-VII.
689. *Chilo suppressalis* (Walker, 1863) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Proletarskiy, Omsk, Nikolaevka, Atmos, Novovarshavka, Buzan. FP: VI-IX.
690. *Calamotropha aureliella* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1841) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Gulyai Pole. FP: VII.
691. *Calamotropha paludella* (Hübner, [1824]) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Listvyagi, Bolshiye Uki, Samsonovo, Gulyai Pole, Knyazev, Proletarskiy, Kabanye2, Davydovka, Ataichye, Ul'zhai, Atmos. FP: VI-VII.
692. *Euchromius gratosella* (Caradja, 1910) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Sholacksor, Atmos. FP: VI-VII.
693. *Euchromius ramburiellus* (Duponchel, 1836) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
694. *Chrysoteuchia culmella* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Tshugunov 1911; Vnukovsky 1930; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Orekhovo, Samsonovo, Sedelnikovo, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Merkutly, Bolshiye Murly, Urusovo, Davydovka, Omsk, Leninsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr'. FP: VI-VII.
695. *Crambus alienellus* (Germar et Kaulfuss, 1817) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Loskutovo, Gulyai Pole, Koshkul'. FP: V-VII.
696. *Crambus heringiellus* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1848) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Petropavlovka. FP: VII.
697. *Crambus lathoniellus* (Zincken, 1817) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Samsonovo, Gulyai Pole, Merkutly, Urusovo, Davydovka. FP: V-VI.
698. *Crambus pascuellus* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Yakovlevka, Gulyai Pole, Knyazev, Davydovka, Omsk, Atmos. FP: VI-VII.
699. *Crambus perlellus* (Scopoli, 1763) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Samsonovo, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Berezka, Urusovo, Davydovka, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos, Alabota. FP: VI-VII.
700. *Crambus pratellus* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
701. *Crambus silvellus* (Hübner, [1813]) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2017. LOC: Buzan. FP: VII.
702. *Agriphila aeneocilliella* (Eversmann, 1844) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Boyevoye, Atrachi, Atmos, Buzan. FP: VIII.
703. *Agriphila poliella* (Treitschke, 1832) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Boyevoye, Davydovka, Syropyatskoye, Ul'zhai, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos. FP: VIII-IX.
704. *Agriphila selasella* (Hübner, [1813]) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Boyevoye, Lyubino, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr'. FP: VII-VIII.

705. *Agriphila straminella* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Samsonovo, Gulyai Pole, Knyazevo, Davydovka, Omsk. FP: VII.
706. *Agriphila tristella* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Davydovka, Omsk, Atmos, Mikhailovka, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Alabota, Buzan. FP: VII-VIII.
707. *Catoptria lythargyrella* (Hübner, 1796) – REF: Vnukovsky 1930; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Atrachi, Knyazevo, Isilkul', Davydovka, Omsk, Ul'zhai, Atmos, Buzan. FP: VII-VIII.
708. *Catoptria permiaea* (W.Petersen, 1924) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Samsonovo, Petropavlovka, Berezka, Boyevoye, Politotdel, Davydovka, Omsk, Novovarshavka, Atmos. FP: VI.
709. *Catoptria verellus* (Zincken, 1817) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2021. LOC: Petropavlovka. FP: VII.
710. *Thisanotia chrysonuchella* (Scopoli, 1763) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Petropavlovka, Davydovka, Novaya Stanitsa, Omsk, Solyanoye, Ataichye, Ul'zhai, Alabota. FP: V-VI.
711. *Pediasia aridella* (Thunberg, 1788) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Knyazevo, Davydovka, Omsk, Ul'zhai, Alabota, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.
712. *Pediasia epineura* (Meyrick, 1883) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr'. FP: VI.
713. *Pediasia kuldjaensis* (Caradja, 1916) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Omsk, Ul'zhai, Sholacksor, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.
714. *Pediasia luteella* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Serebryanoye, Omsk, Ataichye, Ul'zhai, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos, Alabota, Russkaya Polyana. FP: VI-VIII.
715. *Platytes alpinella* (Hübner, [1813]) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Gulyai Pole, Omsk, Atmos Novovarshavka, Buzan. FP: VII-VIII.
716. *Platytes cerussella* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Atrachi, Urusovo, Davydovka, Omsk, Atmos, Alabota. FP: VI.
717. *Talis pulcherrimus* (Staudinger, 1870) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Atmos. FP: VI-VII.
718. *Talis quercella* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Omsk, Kabanye2, Sholacksor, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos, Alabota. FP: VI-VII.

Schoenobiinae

719. *Schoenobius gigantellus* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Urusovo, Knyazevo, Atrachi, Omsk, Ebeity, Amrinskaya Balka, Krasnyi Oktyabr', Atmos, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.
720. *Donacaula forcicella* (Thunberg, 1794) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Maiskyi, Atmos, Buzan. FP: VII-IX.

721. *Donacaula mucronella* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Samsonovo, Sedelnikovo, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Atrachi, Knyazevo, Omsk, Ebeity, Novovarshavka, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.

Scopariinae

722. *Scoparia subfusca* Haworth, 1811 – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Davydovka, Omsk. FP: VI-VIII.

723. *Eudonia lacustrata* (Panzer, 1804) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Davydovka, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Atmos. FP: VII.

724. *Eudonia truncicolella* (Stainton, 1849) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Politotdel, Davydovka, Omsk, Atmos. FP: VII-VIII.

725. *Gesneria centuriella* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Samsonovo, Petropavlovka. FP: VII-VIII.

Acentropinae

726. *Acentria ephemerella* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Gulyai Pole. FP: VII.

727. *Elophila nymphaeata* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Samsonovo, Petropavlovka, Urusovo, Omsk, Kabanye2, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Atmos, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.

728. *Kasania arundinalis* (Eversmann, 1842) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2016. LOC: Ermak. FP: VI.

729. *Cataclysta lemnata* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Atrachi, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr`. FP: VI-VIII.

730. *Parapoyxn stratiotata* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Bolshiye Uki, Petropavlovka, Berezka, Atrachi, Urusovo, Knyazevo, Davydovka, Omsk, Kabanye2, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Atmos. FP: VI-VIII.

731. *Nymphula nitidulata* (Hufnagel, 1767) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Listvyagi, Yakovlevka, Samsonovo, Omsk, Atmos. FP: VII-VIII.

Odontiinae

732. *Atralata albofascialis* (Treitschke, 1829) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Davydovka. FP: VI.

733. *Titanio ledereri* (Staudinger, 1870) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2021. LOC: Solyanoye. FP: VII.

734. *Titanio normalis* (Hübner, 1796) – REF: Knyazev and Ponomarev 2019. LOC: Atmos, Ermak. FP: V, VIII.

Glaphyriinae

735. *Evergestis aenealis* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Omsk, Ermak. FP: VI-VII.
736. *Evergestis extimalis* (Scopoli, 1763) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Bolshiye Uki, Davydovka, Omsk, Kabanye2, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Atmos, Alabota, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.
737. *Evergestis forficalis* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Bolshiye Uki. FP: VI-VII.
738. *Evergestis frumentalis* (Linnaeus, 1761) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Petropavlovka, Davydovka, Podgorodka, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Ataichye. FP: V-VII.
739. *Evergestis pallidata* (Hufnagel, 1767) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Samsonovo, Atrachi, Politotdel, Omsk, Atmos. FP: VII-VIII.
740. *Evergestis politalis* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.

Pyraustinae

741. *Loxostege aeruginalis* (Hübner, 1796) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Davydovka, Sholacksor, Atmos. FP: VI-VII.
742. *Loxostege delibaltica* Szent-Ivány et Uhrík-Meszáros, 1942 – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Ataichye, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Atmos, Buzan. FP: VI-VIII.
743. *Loxostege manualis* (Geyer, 1832) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Alabota. FP: V.
744. *Loxostege peltalis* (Eversmann, 1842) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2021. LOC: Khlebodarovka. FP: V.
745. *Loxostege sticticalis* (Linnaeus, 1761) – REF: Vnukovsky 1926; Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Keizes, Bolshiye Murly, Urusovo, Politotdel, Davydovka, Omsk, Syropyatskoye, Ignatovo, Verkhneilyinka, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Buzan. FP: VI-IX.
746. *Loxostege turbidalis* (Treitschke, 1829) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Urusovo, Davydovka, Omsk, Orlovka, Presnovka, Sholacksor, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Buzan. FP: VI-VII.
747. *Ecpyrrhorrhoe rubiginalis* (Hübner, 1796) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Danilovo, Urusovo, Podgorodka, Davydovka, Ebeity, Nikolaevka, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Atmos. FP: VI-VII.
748. *Paratalanta hyalinalis* (Hübner, 1796) – REF: Tshugunov 1911; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Syropyatskoye, Davydovka. FP: VII.
749. *Paratalanta pandalis* (Hübner, [1825]) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Samsonovo, Sedelnikovo, Gulyai Pole, Bolshiye Murly, Davydovka, Krasnyi Oktyabr`. FP: VI-VIII.

750. *Pyrausta despicata* (Scopoli, 1763) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Berezka, Novotroitskoye, Davydovka, Novaya Stanitsa, Ebeity, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Alabota, Buzan. FP: V-VII.
751. *Pyrausta purpuralis* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Listvyagi, Bolshiye Uki, Samsonovo, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole. FP: V-VIII.
752. *Pyrausta sanguinalis* (Linnaeus, 1767) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Davydovka, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr`. FP: VI-VIII.
753. *Nascia ciliialis* (Hübner, 1796) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Orekhovo, Bolshiye Uki, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole. FP: V-VII.
754. *Sitochroa palealis* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Berezka, Politotdel, Davydovka, Omsk, Sholacksor, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Atmos, Buzan. FP: VII-VIII.
755. *Sitochroa verticalis* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Orekhovo, Samsonovo, Sedelnikovo, Gulyai Pole, Urusovo, Berezka, Davydovka, Omsk, Ebeity, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Alabota. FP: V-VIII.
756. *Sclerocona acutella* (Eversmann, 1842) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Krasnoyarka, Omsk, Atmos. FP: VI.
757. *Psammotis pulveralis* (Hübner, 1796) – REF: Vnukovsky 1930; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole, Knyazev, Davydovka, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr`. FP: VI-VII.
758. *Ostrinia nubilalis* (Hübner, 1796) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Shvetsova 1957; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Sedelnikovo, Elnichnoye, Lyubino, Davydovka, Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Atmos. FP: V-VIII.
759. *Ostrinia palustralis* (Hübner, 1796) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Orekhovo, Bolshiye Uki, Sedelnikovo, Petropavlovka, Gulyai Pole. FP: VI-VII.
760. *Ostrinia peregrinalis* (Eversmann, 1852) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2021. LOC: Karbyza. FP: V-VI.
761. *Ostrinia quadripunctalis* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Samsonovo, Sedelnikovo, Gulyai Pole. FP: VI-VIII.
762. *Ostrinia scapulalis* (Walker, 1859) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Orekhovo, Samsonovo, Elnichnoye, Petropavlovka, Davydovka, Omsk, Atmos. FP: VI-VII.
763. *Anania coronata* (Hufnagel, 1767) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Omsk, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, Atmos. FP: VI.
764. *Anania crocealis* (Hübner, 1796) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Danilovo, Berezka. FP: VI-VII.
765. *Anania funebris* (Ström, 1768) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Bolshiye Uki, Sedelnikovo, Petropavlovka, Bolshiye Murly, Davydovka, Omsk. FP: VI-VII.

766. *Anania fuscalis* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Bolshiye Uki, Gulyai Pole, Urusovo, Davydovka, Omsk. FP: VI-VIII.
767. *Anania hortulata* (Linnaeus, 1758) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Petropavlovka, Bolshiye Murly, Omsk, Buzan. FP: VI.
768. *Anania lancealis* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Vnukovsky 1930; Knyazev et al. 2016. LOC: Yakovlevka, Bolshiye Uki, Omsk. FP: VIII.
769. *Anania luctualis* (Hübner, 1793) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Orekhovo, Petropavlovka, Davydovka, Omsk. FP: V-VII.
770. *Anania perlucidalis* (Hübner, [1809]) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Listvyagi, Samsonovo, Sedelnikovo, Gulyai Pole, Davydovka, Omsk. FP: VI-VII.
771. *Anania stachydalis* (Germar, 1821) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Bolshiye Uki, Sedelnikovo, Petropavlovka, Urusovo, Davydovka. FP: VI-VII.
772. *Anania terrealis* (Treitschke, 1829) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Davydovka, Krasnyi Oktyabr`. FP: VI-VII.
773. *Anania verbascalis* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Ust-Ishim, Samsonovo, Davydovka, Omsk. FP: VI-VII.
774. *Patania ruralis* (Scopoli, 1763) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Samsonovo, Petropavlovka, Muromtsevo, Gulyai Pole, Nalimovo, Davydovka, Omsk, Novovarshevka, Krasnyi Oktyabr`. FP: VII-VIII.
775. *Mecyna flavalis* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Samsonovo, Gulyai Pole, Knyazev, Berezka, Maiskiy, Davydovka, Omsk, Atmos. FP: VII-VIII.
776. *Diasemia reticularis* (Linnaeus, 1761) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Listvyagi. FP: VII.

Spilomelinae

777. *Udea costalis* (Eversmann, 1852) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2019. LOC: Keizes. FP: VII.
778. *Udea decrepitalis* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1848) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2017. LOC: Petropavlovka. FP: VI.
779. *Udea exalbalis* (Caradja, 1916) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Sedelnikovo, Danilovo, Davydovka, Omsk, Kabanye2, Sholacksor, Atmos. FP: VI-VII.
780. *Udea prunalis* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Omsk. FP: VI.
781. *Nomophila noctuella* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775) – REF: Lavrov 1927; Knyazev et al. 2014. LOC: Davydovka, Omsk. FP: VI-VIII.

Conclusion

Thus, the second part of the Catalogue of Lepidoptera of Omsk Region is the largest modern summary of the Microlepidoptera fauna in Western Siberia. The number of Microlepidoptera species (780) found in the Omsk Region is not final and should exceed the number of Macrolepidoptera species (991) by about 1.3 times. Representatives of some families are yet to be found in the Omsk region, among them Micropterigidae, Heliozelidae, Tischeriidae, Douglasiidae, Stathmopodidae, Lypusidae, Chrysopeleidae, Alucitidae, Schreckensteiniidae, Urodidae. Special researches on Microlepidoptera should significantly increase the list of species.

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